

1 Towards Multimodal Geospatial Reasoning: A
2 Foundation Model Approach for Disaster
3 Detection from Social Media, News, and Weather
4 Data

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20 **Abstract**

21 The timely detection of disasters is essential for effective emergency response.
22 Traditional satellite-based monitoring provides accurate hazard observations but
23 suffers from acquisition delays and weather-dependent imaging conditions. There-
24 fore, recent research increasingly uses rapidly available digital data such as
25 social media, news, and weather observations. However, most approaches anal-
26 yse these sources in isolation and lack standardised evaluation. We address this
27 gap using a grid-based framework that quantifies disaster detection accuracy rel-
28 ative to satellite-derived reference data. Within this framework, we introduce
29 a multimodal geospatial reasoning method that employs generative Language
30 Models (LMs) to interpret heterogeneous information. The method integrates

31 Bluesky social media posts, GDELT news headlines, and weather observations
32 through structured prompts and relevance-based data retrieval, framing detec-
33 tion as a binary classification problem on an H3 grid. Across two case studies
34 on the 2024 Central Europe floods and the 2025 Southern California wildfires,
35 LM-based detection outperformed traditional hotspot and anomaly detection
36 while requiring only ten content items per prediction. Results were robust across
37 prompt variants, and Automatic Prompt Optimisation (APO) provided only
38 moderate gains. Overall, this research offers the first systematic evaluation of
39 Bluesky, GDELT, and weather data for disaster detection and shows that Founda-
40 tion Models (FMs) can act as efficient zero-shot or few-shot detectors of
41 natural-hazard-induced disasters.

42 **Keywords:** foundation models, language models, geospatial reasoning, disaster
43 management, event detection

44 1 Introduction

45 As disasters caused by natural hazards such as floods and wildfires increase in both
46 frequency and intensity (Sauerborn & Ebi, 2012), the ability to detect these events in
47 their early stages has become critical for effective emergency response. In this context,
48 *detection* refers to the identification of disasters that are either currently unfolding
49 or imminent. Traditional satellite-based monitoring systems provide accurate obser-
50 vations of disaster extent and impact, but are limited in time-critical scenarios due to
51 fixed acquisition schedules, weather-dependent imaging quality, and resulting delays
52 of up to 24-72 hours (Havas et al., 2017). To overcome these limitations, researchers
53 have turned to more rapidly available social sensing and environmental data sources.
54 Social media platforms provide early, fine-grained reports from individuals on the
55 ground (Hasan, Orgun, & Schwitter, 2019; Z. Wang & Ye, 2018), news aggregators
56 such as Global Database of Events, Language and Tone (GDELT) offer broad situ-
57 ational coverage (Owuor, Hochmair, & Cvetojevic, 2020), and distributed weather
58 sensors deliver high-frequency physical measurements (de Vos, Leijnse, Overeem, &
59 Uijlenhoet, 2017).

60 Many studies have successfully leveraged social media, news or weather data for
61 detecting disaster events. Typically, they combine keyword-based filtering (Stollberg
62 & de Groeve, 2012), threshold approaches (Shah, Yahia, McBride, Jamil, & Dra-
63 heim, 2021), topic modelling (Havas & Resch, 2021), or supervised machine learning
64 (Schmidt, Friedemann, et al., 2025) with spatial hotspot analysis or statistical anomaly
65 detection. While the utility of these methods has been demonstrated on a use-case
66 basis, their performance has rarely been evaluated quantitatively (de Vos et al., 2017;
67 Owuor et al., 2020; Schmidt, Friedemann, et al., 2025). Furthermore, most methods
68 focus on single data sources, with Twitter being the most commonly used platform
69 (Owuor et al., 2020; Schmidt, Friedemann, et al., 2025; Shah et al., 2021), rather than
70 combining multiple data modalities simultaneously.

71 At the same time, large pre-trained Foundation Models (FMs) are increasingly
72 adopted for geospatial tasks. Among these, a particularly important subset consists of

73 Language Models (LMs), which have transformed natural language understanding in
74 recent years. Modern LMs exhibit strong semantic reasoning capabilities, including the
75 ability to interpret spatial relationships when given structured geographic input (Ji,
76 Gao, Nie, Majić, & Janowicz, 2025; Manvi et al., 2024; Schottlander & Shekel, 2025).
77 With in-context learning, they can be utilised in a training-free manner, without the
78 need to collect task-specific data or train models from scratch (McDaniel, Scheele, &
79 Liu, 2024). This makes them especially valuable in fast-evolving scenarios like disasters
80 caused by natural hazards, where labelled data is scarce or unavailable. Despite their
81 ability to integrate and reason across heterogeneous data modalities, LMs have not
82 yet been systematically evaluated for multi-source disaster detection.

83 Our research, therefore, addresses two critical research gaps: (1) the lack of sys-
84 tematic evaluation methods for automated disaster detection from social media, news
85 and weather data, and (2) the limited adoption of LMs and geospatial reasoning for
86 this task. More specifically, we examine the utility of social media data from Bluesky,
87 news headlines from GDELT and historical weather data. This combination represents
88 a step beyond previous studies that typically concentrated on a single data source,
89 often Twitter (e.g. Schmidt, Friedemann, et al., 2025), which has become increasingly
90 difficult to access for researchers (Murtfeldt, Alterman, Kahveci, & West, 2024). Fur-
91 thermore, we explore the capabilities of small-sized generative LMs like Qwen3:14B
92 (Yang et al., 2025) or GPT-5-nano (OpenAI, 2025b) to understand and predict disas-
93 ter occurrence from the mentioned heterogeneous data sources. Our analysis focuses
94 on the September 2024 floods in Central Europe and the January 2025 Southern
95 California wildfires.

96 Accordingly, the central research questions of this paper are as follows:

- 97 • **RQ1:** How effective is the usage of Bluesky social media posts, GDELT news
98 headlines and weather data for detecting disaster events?
- 99 • **RQ2:** To what extent can LMs detect disaster events by reasoning over social media,
100 news and weather data?
- 101 • **RQ3:** How does combining social media, news, and weather data impact disaster
102 detection performance, and which sources contribute most?

103 The core contributions of this study can consequently be summarised as follows:

- 104 • We present the first systematic evaluation of Bluesky social media posts and GDELT
105 news headlines for disaster detection, complemented by weather observations, and
106 evaluated on satellite-derived reference data.
- 107 • Building on the above, we provide an open-access benchmark dataset for multimodal
108 disaster detection.
- 109 • We propose a grid-based evaluation framework that enables the quantitative
110 assessment of disaster detection accuracy using binary classification metrics.
- 111 • We introduce a multimodal geospatial reasoning method that leverages generative
112 LMs for disaster detection from social media, news and weather data.
- 113 • We evaluate different training-free strategies for integrating multiple data modal-
114 ities, comparing ensembles of statistical methods with multimodal fusion directly
115 within the reasoning process of LMs.

116 2 Related work

117 Existing research on disaster detection focuses on diverse digital data sources, espe-
118 cially geo-social media. Additionally, we explore the state-of-the-art of FMs for
119 geospatial reasoning.

120 2.1 Disaster detection from geo-social media

121 Geo-referenced social media data has become a critical resource for disaster detection
122 and management, offering real-time, crowd-sourced information during emergencies
123 (Z. Wang & Ye, 2018). Several studies have demonstrated the practical utility of
124 social media as an alternative data source for detecting events induced by natural
125 hazards (Hasan et al., 2019; Saeed et al., 2019), with some approaches even generating
126 automated disaster alerts. Twitter has been integrated into operational systems like
127 Global Disaster Alert and Coordination System (GDACS) since 2011 (Stollberg &
128 de Groeve, 2012) using relatively simple keyword-filtering methodologies. As a result,
129 relevant information on earthquake-related building collapses can be detected within
130 the first thirty minutes of an event. Building on this foundation, Shah et al. (2021)
131 proposed a threshold-based alert generation system that monitors the ratio of disaster-
132 related, keyword-filtered tweets within an area of interest, triggering alerts when the
133 proportion exceeds 10%.

134 More sophisticated machine learning approaches have also been developed to
135 enhance disaster detection capabilities from geo-social media data. Rezaei, Eslami,
136 Amini, and Eslami (2023) introduced a semi-supervised framework based on a hier-
137 archical attention network, while Havas and Resch (2021) employed Latent Dirichlet
138 Allocation (LDA) to cluster tweets into semantic topics for real-time disaster moni-
139 toring. X. Zhou and Chen (2014) extended this approach by incorporating spatial and
140 temporal dimensions through similarity joins from social media streams. Compara-
141 tive studies by Azlan, Ahmad, Yussof, and Ghapar (2020) evaluated the performance
142 of k -Nearest Neighbour (kNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Naive Bayes
143 algorithms for classifying tweets as disaster events. Deep learning architectures are
144 particularly powerful for such tasks. Pennington et al. (2022) developed a Convo-
145 lutional Neural Network (CNN)-based system for landslides from keyword-filtered
146 Twitter streams, and De Bruijn et al. (2019) utilised Bidirectional Encoder Represent-
147 ations from Transformers (BERT) to create a comprehensive database of flood events
148 from social media posts. Schmidt, Friedemann, et al. (2025) presented a method for
149 wildfire detection based on disaster-relatedness classification of tweets and subsequent
150 hotspot detection. Notably, they found that geo-referenced Twitter data can pro-
151 vide information on wildfires simultaneously or even earlier than official alerts. Pinto,
152 Gonalo Oliveira, Cardoso, and Silva (2023) generated wildfire probability heatmaps
153 in Portugal using a fine-tuned BERT model for extracting fire-related tweets com-
154 bined with location extraction through SpaCy. More generally, new methodologies for
155 location extraction and geoparsing (e.g. Serere & Resch, 2025) increasingly allow for
156 geo-social media analysis across several platforms, even when geo-references are not
157 explicitly present (Vraevi, Schmidt, Keskin, Hanny, & Resch, 2025).

158 Recent advances have also focused on multimodal approaches that integrate text
159 with images or other information for enhanced disaster detection. [J. Li, Wang, and
160 Li \(2022\)](#) proposed a multimodal graph message propagation network based on a
161 [Graph Neural Network \(GNN\)](#) that simultaneously processes both text and images
162 from social media posts. [Koshy and Elango \(2023\)](#) combined fine-tuned [Robustly
163 Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach \(RoBERTa\)](#) models with Vision Transform-
164 ers for multimodal classification using the CrisisMMD dataset, while [Madichetty, M,
165 and Madisetty \(2023\)](#) integrated [RoBERTa](#) with VGG-16 by multiplying output class
166 probabilities from textual and visual components. [Adwaith, Abishake, Raghul, and
167 Sivasankar \(2022\)](#) conducted comprehensive evaluations of various multimodal archi-
168 tectures, finding that [RoBERTa](#) combined with ResNet or DenseNet yielded superior
169 results for disaster-related content processing. Beyond text and images, some studies
170 have incorporated spatial and temporal modalities into their analytical frameworks.
171 [Scheele, Yu, and Huang \(2021\)](#) proposed a [CNN](#)-based text classification approach
172 for disaster-related tweets that includes information about disaster phases and spati-
173 otemporal proximity in the context of Hurricane Sandy. Similarly, [Kaufhold, Bayer,
174 and Reuter \(2020\)](#) integrated text with spatiotemporal non-text features like coordi-
175 nates and distance for binary relevance classification by concatenating them with
176 [term frequency - inverse document frequency \(tf-idf\)](#) vectors and applying a random
177 forest model.

Contribution beyond State of the Art (SotA)

Existing studies on disaster detection from geo-social media primarily rely on Twitter, which has become hardly accessible to researchers since 2023 ([Murtfeldt et al., 2024](#)). Methodologically, they typically employ keyword-based filtering or encoder-based classification combined with spatial statistics, with limited consideration for contextual interrelations across posts and other data sources. To address these limitations, we investigate Bluesky as an alternative social media platform and present a [LM](#)-based disaster detection approach capable of reasoning across multiple content pieces and data sources.

178

179 2.2 Disaster detection from other digital traces

180 In addition to social media, a range of other data sources has been explored for disaster
181 detection and monitoring. One prominent instance is the [GDELT](#) project, which
182 captures worldwide news media reports in 15-minute intervals ([Kalev & Philip, 2013](#)).
183 [Owuor et al. \(2020\)](#) demonstrated that [GDELT](#) data could be effectively utilised to
184 track the progression of Hurricane Dorian across the [United States of America \(USA\)](#).
185 While their analysis revealed that Twitter data provided slightly higher accuracy for
186 the same tracking task, the findings suggest that [GDELT](#) serves as a valuable comple-
187 mentary data source to social media platforms for event detection ([Owuor et al.,
188 2020](#)). Similarly, [Williams \(2020\)](#) analysed [GDELT Global Knowledge Graph \(GKG\)](#)
189 data for two [United Kingdom \(UK\)](#)-based flood and storm events in 2015. They found
190 that while it can provide a timely overview of disaster-affected areas, articles are dif-
191 ficult to filter for disaster-specific content due to broad multi-theme categorisation,

192 and geographic references lack sufficient context to reliably identify relevant loca-
193 tions. [Hammond and Weidmann \(2014\)](#) reported similar challenges when investigating
194 reports of political violence on [GDELT](#). The overall correlation of reports on [GDELT](#)
195 with hand-coded data was mediocre, and reporting coverage was notably geograph-
196 ically biased. [Lu et al. \(2022\)](#) found that media responses towards urban floods in
197 China exhibit strong seasonality on [GDELT](#), and were overall connected with rainfall
198 patterns, with most articles posted during urban flood events.

199 Other digital traces from online platforms have also been utilised for disaster
200 detection. [Steiner and Verborgh \(2015\)](#) developed a language-agnostic system that
201 leverages Wikipedia page edit activity for disaster detection and monitoring in near-
202 real time. However, their method is yet to be evaluated systematically. Similarly, civic
203 service request systems such as 311, a non-emergency municipal hotline for reporting
204 local issues, have been harnessed to monitor localised impacts. [Rainey et al. \(2021\)](#)
205 found that surges in 311 calls during Hurricane Harvey aligned with flood impact, and
206 revealed large shares of impacts outside officially designated floodplains. Moreover,
207 [Zhong, Duckham, Chong, and Tolhurst \(2016\)](#) developed an automated technique for
208 real-time tracking of wildfire perimeters by mining crowdsourced data derived from
209 emergency telephone calls.

210 Crowd-sourced data from mobility, mapping, and sensor platforms have also proved
211 valuable. [Safaei-Moghadam, Tarboton, and Minsker \(2023\)](#) validated flood reports
212 from the community navigation app Waze against several reference datasets and found
213 that the highest correlation of Waze flood reports existed with local surface depres-
214 sions. Other studies demonstrated the utility of Waze reports for situational awareness
215 during Hurricane Harvey ([Lowrie, Kruczkiewicz, McClain, Nielsen, & Mason, 2022](#))
216 and for assessing the trustworthiness of community flood incident reports ([Praharaj
217 et al., 2021](#)). In addition, [Volunteered Geographic Information \(VGI\)](#) initiatives such
218 as [OpenStreetMap \(OSM\)](#) have supported post-disaster mapping, for instance, dur-
219 ing the 2010 Haiti earthquake, where community contributions created essential base
220 maps for emergency responders ([Soden & Palen, 2014](#)). Subsequent research has
221 assessed the completeness of [OSM](#) data in countries with high risk of disasters, finding
222 significant quality challenges ([Goldblatt, Jones, & Mannix, 2020](#)). Besides mapping
223 and mobility, community-based weather reporting platforms and distributed sensor
224 networks have become increasingly important. Networks of weather stations provide
225 dense, real-time rainfall and wind observations, which have been successfully employed
226 in disaster contexts ([de Vos et al., 2017](#)). [Khaing Kyaw et al. \(2024\)](#) found that crowd-
227 sourced rainfall data can produce significantly more accurate inundation maps than
228 those generated from official rain gauges. For wildfires, [Bhamra et al. \(2023\)](#) developed
229 an ensemble approach for multimodal smoke detection using weather sensor measure-
230 ments together with satellite-based fire detections and optical camera images. Lastly,
231 crowd-sourced seismology systems combine user website, app, or social media usage
232 with seismic network data to provide more reliable earthquake localisation ([Bondár
233 et al., 2020](#); [Bossu et al., 2018](#); [Steed et al., 2019](#))

Contribution beyond SOTA

Previous studies have mostly investigated individual data sources in isolation and lack a quantitative evaluation that covers multiple disaster events. To overcome these limitations, we systematically integrate social media posts, news headlines, and weather data, and present a grid-based evaluation methodology that evaluates disaster detection performance across two real-world scenarios, while leveraging the reasoning capabilities of LMs for this task.

234

2.3 Foundation models for geospatial reasoning

235

236 Significant advances in FMs have shifted the focus from task-specific models to large,
237 pre-trained backbones. These models can be quickly adapted to diverse tasks across
238 several domains, including the geospatial sciences (Mai et al., 2024). While much
239 of this progress has initially centred on remote sensing, with geospatial FMs such
240 as NASA/IBM’s Prithvi (Jakubik et al., 2023), more recent research has increas-
241 ingly explored the adoption of language FMs and multimodal FMs within Geospatial
242 Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI). For instance, Ji et al. (2025) investigated how general-
243 purpose generative LMs such as GPT-3.5-turbo, GPT-4, and DeepSeek-R1-14B can
244 interpret spatial relationships when given vector data in Well-Known-Text (WKT)
245 format. Using in-context learning, GPT-4 achieved over 0.66 accuracy in identifying
246 topological spatial relations (e.g. containment, adjacency), while also demonstrating
247 an ability to translate informal place descriptions into formal spatial relationships.
248 Similarly, Manvi et al. (2024) presented GeoLLM, a method for geospatial knowledge
249 extraction from LMs with auxiliary map data from OpenStreetMap. They were able
250 to achieve an up to 70% improvement over a nearest-neighbour baseline, and parity
251 with satellite-based prediction benchmarks.

252 Despite these promising results in descriptive and inferential tasks, several studies
253 caution that unmodified FMs might still be challenged with more complex geospa-
254 tial assignments. L. Xu et al. (2025) evaluated six state-of-the-art LMs across twelve
255 such tasks, and found that their performance generally decreased with increasing task
256 complexity. In particular, most models did not perform well on tasks requiring high-
257 level reasoning, such as route planning. Mai et al. (2024) evaluated both multimodal
258 and language FMs across a similar range of geospatial tasks. They found that on sim-
259 ple tasks that only involve text, such as toponym recognition, task-agnostic FMs can
260 outperform supervised models in a zero-shot or few-shot learning setting. However,
261 on more complex tasks with multiple data modalities, like urban noise intensity clas-
262 sification using street view images, the FMs underperformed. Notably, most existing
263 attempts to enable geospatial reasoning in FMs have primarily relied on in-context
264 learning with generative LMs, where spatial relationships are introduced through
265 examples or auxiliary descriptions provided at inference time. To enable more complex
266 tasks, Google recently introduced their own agentic geospatial reasoning framework
267 (Schottlander & Shekel, 2025). It decomposes queries into subtasks, invokes the most

268 suitable task-specific model or geospatial service, like mapping [Application Program-](#)
269 [ming Interfaces \(APIs\)](#) or spatial databases, and then integrates the outputs into
270 coherent responses using Google Gemini ([Anil et al., 2024](#)).

271 In disaster management, the adoption of large-scale [FMs](#) for geospatial reason-
272 ing is still in the early stages. [Yin, Xue, Liu, Li, and Werner \(2025\)](#) proposed an
273 [LM-enhanced](#) method for disaster geolocalisation that considers both explicit and
274 implicit geoinformation for multimodal social media data. [Lei et al. \(2025\)](#) highlighted
275 how encoder-based, decoder-based, and multimodal [FMs](#) are increasingly applied to
276 understand disaster-related content and geospatial context, but also for report gen-
277 eration and response planning. [F. Xu, Ma, Li, and Cheng \(2025\)](#) further found that
278 [LMs](#) are particularly effective for screening unstructured, multilingual disaster-related
279 communications and integrating multimodal information streams.

Contribution beyond SOTA

Existing geospatial reasoning approaches have not been systematically investi-
gated or evaluated in the context of disaster detection. To address this gap,
our research proposes and quantitatively evaluates a methodology that lever-
ages generative [LMs](#) for disaster detection from social media, news and weather
data. The approach integrates these data sources through geospatial reason-
ing. We furthermore conduct a comprehensive evaluation of different [LMs](#) and
data retrieval strategies.

280

281 3 Materials and methods

282 Our methodology focuses on multimodal, multi-source disaster detection using geospa-
283 tial reasoning with generative [LMs](#). We formulate event detection as a binary
284 classification problem based on H3 grid cells ([Uber, 2023](#)). These are hexagonal spatial
285 units that partition the Earth’s surface into uniform regions at multiple hierarchi-
286 cal scales. We chose the hexagonal grid format as it provides clearer neighbourhood
287 relationships than rectangular grids and seamless global coverage ([Birch, Oom, &](#)
288 [Beecham, 2007](#)). For this particular study, we used H3 grid resolution 4 with an aver-
289 age edge length of 26.07 kilometres. This resolution offered the best trade-off between
290 spatial granularity and data availability. Finer grids suffered from notable data spar-
291 sity, while coarser grids merged heterogeneous areas and failed to capture localised
292 disaster impacts. Moreover, resolution 4 aligns well with the typical spatial extent
293 of local disasters, which often span areas on the order of several tens of kilometres
294 ([de Albuquerque, Herfort, Brenning, & Zipf, 2015](#); [Sakaki, Okazaki, & Matsuo, 2010](#);
295 [Schmidt, Friedemann, et al., 2025](#)). The overall framework enables the quantitative
296 evaluation of disaster detection performance using standard classification metrics such
297 as precision, recall, and F1-score.

298 Our study design is illustrated in Fig. 1. It can be summarised as follows:

- 299 1. We gathered satellite-based hazards extents from [National Aeronautics and Space](#)
300 [Administration \(NASA\)](#) and [German Aerospace Center \(DLR\)](#), social media

- 301 posts from Bluesky, news headlines from [GDELT](#), and weather observations from
 302 Meteostat for two distinct disaster events from across the world.
- 303 2. To facilitate a quantitative evaluation of disaster detection methods, we defined an
 304 H3 evaluation grid and aggregated all data points in their cells.
- 305 3. We established state-of-the-art statistical approaches as a baseline for disaster
 306 detection based on previous research.
- 307 4. We designed a geospatial reasoning methodology with generative [LMs](#) to predict
 308 disaster occurrence within each H3 cell using multimodal data from all sources
 309 simultaneously.

Fig. 1 Methodological overview of our study.

310 3.1 Data collection

311 Our study events were selected to cover two distinct recent disaster events with
 312 different geographic and linguistic contexts. More specifically, we considered the
 313 September 2024 floods in Central Europe and the January 2025 wildfires in Southern
 314 California ([USA](#)). The two disasters can be described as follows, and were extensively
 315 covered on social media (e.g. [Erokhin, 2025](#); [Wojtasińska-Żygadło et al., 2025](#)) and in
 316 news reports (e.g. [Henley, 2024](#); [Milman, Swan, Paz, & Scruton, 2025](#)):

- 317 1. **2024 Central Europe floods:** In September 2024, Storm Boris generated
 318 unprecedented rainfall across Central Europe. The most severe impacts occurred
 319 between September 12 to 16, when extreme precipitation ranging up to 400 mm
 320 was recorded in some regions. This caused severe flooding events across Aus-
 321 tria, Czechia, Slovakia, Poland, Romania, and Hungary. The floods led to at
 322 least 27 fatalities and inflicted widespread infrastructural damage, with estimated

323 economic costs of 4.2 billion € (Austrian Ministry of Agriculture, Regions and
324 Tourism, 2024; Maskell, 2024).

325 2. **2025 Southern California (SoCal) wildfires:** In January 2025, a complex
326 of 14 wildfires erupted across Southern California, impacting the Los Angeles
327 metropolitan area and San Diego County. During the peak fire activity from
328 January 7 to 31, extreme weather conditions, including prolonged drought, low
329 humidity, and Santa Ana winds exceeding 160 km/h, created optimal fire propaga-
330 tion conditions. The wildfire complex resulted in at least 30 fatalities, displaced over
331 200,000 residents, destroyed more than 18,000 buildings, and burned over 230 km²
332 of land (California Department of Forestry and Fire Protection, 2025; US EPA,
333 2025).

334 3.1.1 Satellite-based hazard extents

335 Satellite-based hazard extents were used as independent reference data for our anal-
336 ysis. We collected comprehensive datasets for both of our disaster events to establish
337 a foundation for downstream processing. For the 2024 Central Europe floods, we
338 derived surface water bodies from all available Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite
339 images acquired between September 1 and 30, 2024, using the method described in
340 Wieland et al. (2024). To differentiate temporary flooded hazard areas from perma-
341 nent water bodies, we subtracted a reference water mask derived from the two previous
342 years using the method introduced by Martinis, Groth, Wieland, Knopp, and Rät-
343 tich (2022). Together, the satellite data provides a resolution of 10 m and a revisit
344 rate of 1 to 3 days for the area of interest. For the 2025 Southern California wild-
345 fires, we obtained active wildfire data from NASA Land, Atmosphere Near real-time
346 Capability for Earth observation (LANCE) Fire Information for Resource Manage-
347 ment System (FIRMS) (NASA LANCE, 2023) for the period from December 24, 2024
348 to February 14, 2025. The system processes Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectro-
349 radiometer (MODIS) data from NASA’s Terra and Aqua satellites four times daily at
350 mid-latitudes, delivering active fire detections at 1 km resolution.

351 3.1.2 Bluesky posts

352 The decentralised microblogging platform Bluesky (Kleppmann et al., 2024) serves as
353 our primary social media data source for this study due to several advantages. Most
354 importantly, the platform provides open API access for research purposes, in contrast
355 to the now restricted access policies of X (formerly Twitter), which have significantly
356 limited academic research since 2023 (Murfeldt et al., 2024). Additionally, Bluesky’s
357 microblogging format, including a 300-character limitation per post, closely mirrors
358 Twitter’s structure. This enables the adaptation of established social media anal-
359 ysis methodologies from Twitter-based research, while ensuring comparability with
360 existing studies.

361 We collected social media data using the `app.bsky.feed.searchPosts` API end-
362 point, which enables textual keyword-based queries with temporal filtering. Due to a
363 dysfunctional `cursor` parameter at the time of data collection in April 2025 (bluesky-
364 social GitHub, 2024), the endpoint was limited to returning a maximum of 100 posts
365 per query. We therefore created an iterative crawling algorithm (Algorithm 1) that

366 systematically queries keywords across specified time intervals in 30-minute steps.
 367 Preliminary testing confirmed that this interval size consistently returned fewer than
 368 100 posts, ensuring no data loss due to [API](#) limitations.

Algorithm 1: Iterative algorithm for Bluesky data collection

Input: keyword list Q , time interval $[t_{\min}, t_{\max}]$, crawling interval $s = 30$ minutes
Output: Complete set of Bluesky posts P
 $P = \{\}$;
foreach keyword q in Q **do**
 369 **for** time t from t_{\min} to t_{\max} in steps of s **do**
 posts = `app.bsky.feed.searchPosts`($q = q$, since = t , to =
 $t + s$, limit = 100);
 $P = P \cup$ posts;
 end
end
return P

370 Our keyword list Q was curated together with disaster management experts to
 371 account for both event characteristics and linguistic diversity (Table 1). For the
 372 2024 Central Europe floods, we employed disaster-specific terms across the national
 373 languages of the six most affected countries: Austria (German), Czechia and Slovakia
 374 (Czech/Slovak), Poland (Polish), Romania (Romanian), and Hungary (Hungarian).
 375 For the 2025 Southern California wildfires, we focused on English terms, following the
 376 same principle of using each region’s official language. The selected keywords were
 377 also informed by [Hanny, Schmidt, and Resch \(2024\)](#), who demonstrated the effec-
 378 tiveness of such keywords for identifying disaster-related tweets. However, keyword
 379 searches can still yield many false positives that compromise data quality. Therefore,
 380 we employed it merely as an initial pre-filtering step necessitated by the Bluesky [API](#),
 381 and applied downstream disaster-relatedness classification using a fine-tuned XLM-
 382 RoBERTa model ([Hanny et al., 2024](#)). The model was specifically developed for binary
 383 disaster-relatedness classification of multilingual social media posts. It was fine-tuned
 384 with 179,591 labelled tweets in 5 languages from 24 disaster events across the world,
 385 including floods, wildfires and storms. After training, it achieved an accuracy of 0.8
 386 to 0.96 across all tested events, making it highly robust across disasters and geo-
 387 graphic contexts. The downstream classification also mitigates differences in keyword
 388 specificity, as the keywords primarily served to obtain a large enough sample (here,
 389 >100,000 posts) for quantitative analysis. Data collection periods were aligned with
 390 our satellite data acquisition time frames to ensure temporal consistency across data
 391 sources.

392 This methodology yielded 105,767 posts for the 2024 Central Europe floods and
 393 570,570 posts for the 2025 Southern California wildfires. The substantial volume differ-
 394 ence reflects two key platform dynamics: Bluesky’s rapid user growth from 10 million
 395 users in September 2024 to over 30 million since the beginning of 2025 ([Bluesky, 2024](#),
 396 [2025](#)), and the platform’s geographic bias, with 42.27% of all Bluesky visits originat-
 397 ing from the [USA](#) in November 2024, followed by Brazil (11.01%), the [UK](#) (7.51%),
 398 Japan (6.18%), and Germany (3.21%) ([Duarte, 2025](#)).

Table 1 Disaster-specific keywords used for Bluesky data collection. Each event column shows the keywords used for content retrieval, grouped by category. The temporal filtering periods are indicated in italics beneath the event headers.

Keyword category	2024 Central Europe floods <i>September 5-30, 2024</i>	2025 SoCal wildfires <i>December 24, 2024 - February 14, 2025</i>
Event type	flood, flut, überschwemmung, hochwasser, povodeň, zaplavení, zaplaveni, powódź, zalenie, inundație, inundare, árvíz, elöntés	fire, wildfire, firestorm, brush fire, forest fire, blaze, inferno
Location terms	<i>No specific location terms were used to avoid geographic bias, as the floods were geographically widespread.</i>	southern california, los angeles, san diego, social
Environmental conditions	rain, regen, déšť, dážď, deszcz, ploaie, eső, boris (storm name)	santa ana, drought, low humidity, red flag warning
Impact and response terms	evac, evakuierung, evakuace, evakuácia, ewakuacja, evacuar, evakuálás rescue, rettung, záchrana, ratunek, salvare, mentés fatality, todesfall, úmrtí, ofiara śmiertelna, deces, haláleset damage, schäden, škody, szkody, daune, kár economic losses, verluste, ztráty, straty, pierderi, veszteségek	evac, fatality, homes destroyed, smoke plume, air quality
Event-specific hashtags	<i>None identified, to limited hashtag adoption in Central Europe during the study period.</i>	#californiawildfires, #cafire, #socialfires, #sandiegofire, #santaanawinds

399 After collecting the Bluesky posts, we applied two main processing steps. First, we
400 used geoparsing to extract spatial references from post content. This involved using the
401 Irchel Geoparser (Gomes, 2024) with spaCy’s (Montani, Honnibal, Boyd, Landeghem,
402 & Peters, 2023) `xx_ent_wiki_sm` Named Entity Recognition (NER) model (F-score
403 0.83) for the September 2024 Central Europe floods and the `en_core_web_trf` NER
404 model (F-score 0.90) for the January 2025 Southern California wildfires. Multiple
405 extracted locations per post were converted into multipoint geometries, which are
406 treated equivalently to multiple individual points in subsequent analysis. Notably, our
407 methodology interprets these extracted geolocations as references to places mentioned
408 in the content rather than as indicators of the user’s physical position. Although meth-
409 ods to distinguish in-situ from remote reporting exist (Serere & Resch, 2025), they do
410 not yet support multiple languages and rely on geocoding with Google Maps, which
411 would cost over 1,000 € for our data. After geoparsing, we applied disaster-relatedness
412 classification using the Disaster-Twitter-XLM-RoBERTa-AL model by Hanny et al.
413 (2024). The model achieved high accuracy (0.80-0.96) across multiple disaster-related
414 social media datasets and languages, including English, German, and other European
415 languages relevant to our study areas.

416 3.1.3 GDELT news data

417 To complement social media data with news coverage, we collected news headlines
418 from the GDELT v2 full text API and GKG. Specifically, we utilised GDELT’s
419 thematic classification system and selected disaster-related themes as initial filters
420 (Table A1 in the appendix). We then queried the API for each theme on each day
421 within our temporal boundaries, retrieving up to 250 article links daily. This rep-
422 resented the API’s limit as of May 2025. The resulting dataset contained article
423 metadata such as the title, Uniform Resource Locators (URLs) and publication dates,
424 but not yet geographic references. To obtain those, we queried the GDELT GKG
425 dataset for the same date ranges, using the collected article URLs to identify corre-
426 sponding entries. We subsequently extracted and parsed the locations mentioned in
427 the article, which are provided as point coordinates. Again, these locations are viewed
428 as places being discussed in the content. If multiple locations were referenced within
429 a single article, we aggregated them into a multipoint geometry to represent the full
430 spatial scope. Notably, GDELT entries often contain multiple themes, and geographic
431 references may not directly relate to disaster contexts. The described data retrieval
432 strategy, therefore, serves merely as a broad pre-filtering step.

433 Overall, we retrieved 28,556 news headlines for the 2024 Central Europe floods,
434 9,951 (34.85%) of which contained geographic references. For the 2025 Southern
435 California wildfires, we obtained 30,151 headlines, of which 17,514 (58.09%) had
436 geographic references. After collection, we applied disaster-relatedness classification
437 (Hanny et al., 2024) to the headlines to distinguish genuinely disaster-related content
438 from other material.

439 3.1.4 Weather observations

440 In addition to Bluesky social media posts and GDELT news headlines, we collected
441 historical weather observations to provide environmental context. Using Meteostat
442 (Lamprecht, n.d.), we retrieved daily weather data for the centroid of each H3 cell
443 covering all areas of interest defined in Sec. 3.1. For the 2024 Central Europe floods,
444 we collected data from September 5 to 30, 2024, covering Austria, Czechia, Slovakia,
445 Poland, Romania, and Hungary. For the 2025 Southern California wildfires, data was
446 collected from December 24, 2024 to February 14, 2025, encompassing all H3 cells
447 within California. We collected daily precipitation (mm), minimum, maximum, and
448 average temperatures (°C), and wind speed (km/h).

449 3.2 Data aggregation

450 Our initial data collection covered large geographic areas to ensure comprehensive
451 representation of both disaster events. However, exploratory analysis revealed signifi-
452 cant data sparsity in certain regions, particularly for Bluesky posts and GDELT news
453 headlines in Eastern Europe. Additionally, the initial collection included large periph-
454 eral areas like Northern California with little or no relevance to the disaster impacts.
455 To address these constraints, we defined targeted H3 evaluation grids for both dis-
456 aster events. For the 2024 Central Europe floods, we concentrated on Austria and
457 Czechia during the primary flood occurrence period from September 7 to 21, 2024.

458 These countries demonstrated the best coverage of geo-referenced Bluesky posts and
459 [GDELT](#) headlines and were affected most by the flood ([Maskell, 2024](#)). For the 2025
460 Southern California wildfires, we selected ten Southern California counties (Imperial,
461 Kern, Los Angeles, Orange, Riverside, San Bernardino, San Diego, San Luis Obispo,
462 Santa Barbara, and Ventura) from January 1 to 15, 2025. This temporal window cap-
463 tures the initial outbreak and peak destructive spread of major fires, including the
464 Palisades and Eaton fires that started on January 7. We excluded the later contain-
465 ment period when [NASA FIRMS](#) data became less available due to reduced visible
466 fire activity ([Starr & Morton, 2025](#)). Finally, to ensure temporal consistency between
467 social media, news and satellite ground-reference data, we restricted evaluation to H3
468 cells with same-day satellite coverage.

469 Subsequently, we aggregated all retrieved data using our H3 grid. For Bluesky
470 social media posts and [GDELT](#) news headlines, we computed the daily number of
471 posts and news items whose (multi)point locations intersected with the H3 cell geom-
472 etry. Additionally, we calculated the number of disaster-related posts and headlines.
473 Weather data was already aggregated per cell and day and only needed to be fil-
474 tered by spatial and temporal boundaries. The satellite-based hazard extents were
475 used to assign each H3 grid cell daily reference values, indicating whether there was a
476 significant ongoing flood or wildfire. To achieve this, we cross-checked different thresh-
477 old values of flooded areas or active fires with official reference data sources about
478 the individual disasters. For the 2024 Central Europe floods use case, we found that
479 smaller flooded areas were detected quite frequently, even at times without major
480 flood reports. We therefore detected a significant flood event only if there were ≥ 50
481 delineated flood blobs within a cell. This most closely reflected the flooded areas,
482 as reported by government entities ([Austrian Ministry of Agriculture, Regions and
483 Tourism, 2024](#)). For the Southern California wildfires, we found that a threshold ≥ 1
484 active fire was sufficient to mirror the wildfire activity reported by the California Fire
485 Department ([California Department of Forestry and Fire Protection, 2025](#)).

486 We furthermore conducted a sensitivity analysis to validate our threshold selec-
487 tions. In this analysis, we systematically adjusted the flood threshold across a range
488 of 1 to 100 delineated flood blobs and the wildfire threshold from 1 to 25 active fire
489 detections (see Fig. C5 in the appendix for details). For the Central Europe floods,
490 the percentage of positive cells differed only minimally between thresholds of 40 and
491 60 blobs, informing our chosen threshold of 50. For the Southern California wildfires,
492 the fraction of positive cells drops sharply from approximately 2.4% at a threshold of
493 1 to below 1% at a threshold of 2, after which it remains comparatively stable. We
494 therefore selected a threshold of 1 to avoid discarding genuine wildfire activity.

495 Table 2 provides an overview of our data, including the proportion of cells
496 with satellite-derived ongoing floods or wildfires. Notably, there is a significant class
497 imbalance. This is expected as disasters are usually geographically and temporally
498 constrained ([Meriläinen & Koro, 2021](#)). Fig. 2 additionally illustrates the spatial
499 extent and hexagonal structure of both evaluation grids, along with the corresponding
500 disaster footprints from satellite observations.

Table 2 Number H3 evaluation cells with same-day satellite reference data, and the number/fraction of cells with ongoing flood or wildfire activity.

Use case	#Cells	#Disaster cells
2024 Central Europe floods	794	92 (11.59%)
2025 Southern California wildfires	1,230	30 (2.44%)

Fig. 2 H3 evaluation grids overlaid with satellite-derived flood and wildfire data for both case studies. Each hexagonal cell represents one H3 resolution 4 unit with approximately 26.07 km edge length. Cell counts and ground-reference data are the totals over the entire study period.

501 3.3 Statistical event detection

502 As state-of-the-art baselines for comparative evaluation, we implemented three sta-
 503 tistical approaches for disaster event detection, with each utilising a different data
 504 modality.

505 *Social media hotspot detection.*

506 Following the methodology by Schmidt, Friedemann, et al. (2025), we computed the
 507 daily fraction of disaster-related Bluesky posts within each H3 grid cell, normalising
 508 by total post volume. This approach identifies spatial clusters of heightened disaster-
 509 related activity through the local Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic (Eq. 1) (Getis & Ord, 1992)
 510 with Queen weights. In the formula, x_j is the attribute value of feature j , $w_{i,j}$ is the
 511 spatial weight between feature i and j and n is the total number of features. \bar{X} is the
 512 mean of all feature values and S is the population standard deviation (Eq. 2)

513 We detect a disaster event in a cell when the hotspot analysis yields a p -value
 514 ≤ 0.01 and a z -score ≥ 1.645 , as validated by Schmidt, Friedemann, et al. (2025).

$$G_i^* = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n w_{i,j} x_j - \bar{X} \sum_{j=1}^n w_{i,j}}{S \sqrt{\frac{(n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{i,j}^2 - (\sum_{j=1}^n w_{i,j})^2)}{n-1}}} \quad (1)$$

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n x_j^2}{n} - (\bar{X})^2} \quad (2)$$

515 To obtain an additional probability-like measure of detected hotspots, we used
 516 Eq. 3. It transforms the statistical significance values into scores within the range of
 517 $[0, 1]$, reflecting the confidence with which the hotspot was detected.

$$\hat{p}(\text{hotspot}) = \begin{cases} 1 - p_{G_i^*} & \text{if } z_{G_i^*} \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

518 ***GDELT news hotspot detection.***

519 We applied the same statistical methodology on our [GDELT](#) data, computing the
 520 daily fraction of disaster-related news headlines within each H3 grid cell. The approach
 521 employs the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic (Eq. 1) with identical detection thresholds (p -
 522 value ≤ 0.01 , z -score ≥ 1.645), and uses the same probability estimate transformation
 523 (Eq. 3).

524 ***Weather anomaly detection.***

525 As an additional statistical baseline, we performed anomaly detection based on long-
 526 term weather observations. Specifically, we collected daily precipitation, temperature,
 527 and wind speed data from Meteostat ([Lamprecht, n.d.](#)) for the past 30 years. For each
 528 disaster event, we extracted the records corresponding to the same calendar month and
 529 aggregated them for every H3 cell in the evaluation grid. This served as the baseline.

530 Flood weather anomalies were detected when daily precipitation (P) exceeded the
 531 99th percentile of the month-specific historical distribution ($z_P \geq 2.326$). This thresh-
 532 old choice is consistent with the [Standardised Precipitation Index \(SPI\)](#) framework of
 533 [McKee, Doesken, and Kleist \(1993\)](#), which defines extreme wet anomalies as rare high-
 534 percentile events. It is also in line with more recent extreme precipitation detection
 535 methods ([H. Li et al., 2022](#)).

536 Wildfire weather anomalies were identified under compound conditions: temper-
 537 ature (T) above the 90th percentile ($z_T \geq 1.282$), wind speed (W) above the 80th
 538 percentile ($z_W \geq 0.842$), and precipitation (P) below the 10th percentile ($z_P \geq$
 539 -1.282). These thresholds follow previous wildfire anomaly detection methods, which
 540 highlight the combined role of heat, wind, and dryness ([Abatzoglou, Williams, &
 541 Barbero, 2019](#); [Barbero, Abatzoglou, Larkin, Kolden, & Stocks, 2015](#); [Van Wagner,
 542 1987](#)).

543 To quantify the degree of anomaly, we additionally computed probability-like
 544 scores based on the empirical [Cumulative Distribution Functions \(CDFs\)](#) $F(\cdot)$ for
 545 precipitation, temperature, and wind speed using Eq. 4 for floods and Eq. 5 for
 546 wildfires.

$$\hat{p}(\text{flood}) = \begin{cases} 1 - F_P(x_P) & \text{if } z_P \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$\hat{p}(\text{wildfire}) = \begin{cases} \min \{1 - F_T(x_T), 1 - F_W(x_W), F_P(x_P)\} & \text{if } z_T \geq 0 \wedge \\ & z_W \geq 0 \wedge \\ & z_P \leq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

547 3.4 Geospatial reasoning

548 Recent research highlights the potential of large, pre-trained **FMs**, in particular gener-
 549 ative **LMs**, for understanding disaster-related online communication (McDaniel et al.,
 550 2024) and reasoning across geographic space (Ji et al., 2025). We therefore hypoth-
 551 esised that **LMs** can effectively act as human-like judges to detect ongoing disasters
 552 based on multimodal evidence from social media, news, and weather observations.
 553 In contrast to the statistical approaches described above, geospatial reasoning with
 554 **LMs** circumvents the limitation of directly interpreting statistical anomalies as ongo-
 555 ing disasters. Moreover, pre-trained **LMs** are substantially more data-efficient, as they
 556 can interpret social media posts, news headlines, or weather information directly in
 557 the context of the task at hand. These models additionally have factual knowledge
 558 acquired during pre-training (H. Chang et al., 2024). This data efficiency is particu-
 559 larly advantageous in disaster event detection, where rapid and accurate predictions
 560 are crucial, and extensive data collection may not be feasible.

561 To leverage the geospatial reasoning capabilities of **LMs**, we developed an in-
 562 context learning approach that processes data from all sources from a given day within
 563 a single prompt, as outlined below. We assumed that this integrated approach would
 564 enable the **LM** to identify interdependencies between social media, news, and weather
 565 data that sequential processing methods might overlook. A visual overview of our **LM**
 566 setup is provided in Fig. 3

Fig. 3 Methodological setup of our LM-based geospatial reasoning approach for disaster detection.

Our prompt architecture comprises a system prompt with task instructions, paired with a structured user prompt containing four information blocks:

1. **event metadata** specifying the disaster type (flood or wildfire), H3 centroid coordinates with human-readable location resolved through Nominatim reverse geocoding (Nominatim contributors, 2025), and date;
2. **social media**, providing aggregated statistics on total posts within the cell and the percentage of disaster-related posts, followed by a set of selected Bluesky posts;
3. **GDELT news data**, similarly structured with total article counts, disaster-related percentage, and a set of selected GDELT headlines;
4. **weather observations** presenting meteorological conditions on the day of interest, including temperature, precipitation, and wind speed measurements for the target cell.

Given the limited context window of LMs, a data retrieval strategy which selects the most relevant data for the prompt was required. We implemented two strategies to realise this:

- **Cell-based:** This baseline approach selects the top n social media posts and news headlines located within the target H3 cell on the evaluation day, ranked by their disaster-relatedness classification scores, with disaster-related content prioritised.
- **Score-based:** This approach addresses the uneven spatial distribution of data by considering content from neighbouring cells when local observations are sparse.

587 For each Bluesky post or GDELT news headline m , we compute a relevance score
588 $R(m; c, d)$ for the target H3 cell c on the evaluation day d as shown in Eq. 6. The
589 score depends on three factors:

- 590 1. temporal recency $a(m; d)$ defined as the age of the content in hours relative to
591 day d , with $a(m; d) = 0$ if the content was posted on the same day;
- 592 2. spatial proximity $\Delta(m; c)$, defined as the Haversine distance (Inman, 1858) in
593 kilometres between the content-extracted location and the centroid of H3 cell c ,
594 with $\Delta(m; c) = 0$ if the content lies within the same cell); and
- 595 3. disaster-relatedness $s(m)$, where $s(m) = 1$ if the content is disaster-related and
596 $s(m) = 0$ otherwise.

$$R(m; c, d) = -[(a(m; d) + 1) \cdot (\Delta(m; c) + 1) + M \cdot (1 - s(m))] \quad (6)$$

597 M is a large constant greater the maximum possible value of R , ensuring that
598 disaster-related content always outranks non-disaster content. The formula further-
599 more guarantees that recent and spatially close content receives higher relevance,
600 while older and distant content is penalised. During prompt generation, the n social
601 media posts and news headlines with highest scores are selected.

602 For both retrieval strategies, we employed the same disaster-relatedness classifier
603 (Hanny et al., 2024) as for statistical hotspot detection. This choice was motivated
604 by the low inference times during data retrieval compared to much larger generative
605 LMs, while providing reliably high classification accuracy. In addition, using a shared
606 classifier ensures methodological consistency, allowing us to isolate the effects of LM-
607 based geospatial reasoning from differences in disaster-relatedness assessment.

608 Figs. B1 and B2 in the appendix illustrate the user prompt templates for both cell-
609 based and score-based data retrieval strategies. For the second strategy, individual
610 social media posts and news headlines were formatted with contextual spatial and
611 temporal information as “distance_km= \cdot | hours_ago= \cdot | \cdot ” to facilitate geospatial
612 reasoning using proximity.

613 To come up with a suitable system prompt, we followed a multi-step procedure.
614 First, two domain experts with experience in disaster management designed a base
615 prompt. It is depicted in Fig. B3 in the appendix, and defines the task along with
616 the desired output. The model was instructed to return a JavaScript Object Notation
617 (JSON) object containing (1) a binary disaster prediction label, (2) a probability esti-
618 mate, and (3) a concise summary of its rationale. We then evaluated this prompt across
619 eight state-of-the-art Small Language Models (SLMs) over multiple runs: Qwen3:8B
620 and Qwen3:14B (Yang et al., 2025), Deepseek-R1:8B and Deepseek-R1:14B (Guo et
621 al., 2025), GPT-4.1-nano (OpenAI, 2025a), GPT-5-nano (OpenAI, 2025b), Gemma
622 3:12B (Kamath et al., 2025), and Llama3.1:8B (Dubey et al., 2024). To ensure com-
623 putational efficiency, the validation step was conducted using a stratified validation
624 subset comprising 10% (202 samples) of the evaluation data. The models were selected
625 because they offer high inference speed and can be deployed on consumer-grade hard-
626 ware, making them most suitable for real-time deployment at scale. Throughout model
627 validation, we used the score-based data retrieval method with $n = 10$ to facilitate

628 geospatial reasoning while keeping the prompt size reasonable. Subsequently, we eval-
629 uated different values of $n \in \{5, 10, 15, 20\}$ with the best-performing model to ensure
630 it receives sufficient content in the prompt to make reliable predictions. The selected
631 model and most suitable n served as the basis for [Automatic Prompt Optimisation](#)
632 ([APO](#)), following the methodology of [Y. Zhou et al. \(2023\)](#) and [Pryzant et al. \(2023\)](#).

633 For [APO](#), we employed a class-balanced subset of 50 H3 cells per disaster (25
634 disaster-positive and 25 disaster-negative), which was obtained using stratified ran-
635 dom sampling from our full evaluation data. This balancing ensured that macro F1,
636 our optimisation objective, was computed on a stable and representative sample of
637 both classes, rather than being affected by random fluctuations due to class imbal-
638 ance. The [APO](#) algorithm itself is iterative. Starting with the human-designed base
639 prompt, one [LM](#) generates critiques of the prompt based on misclassified examples,
640 and a second [LM](#) produces five improved candidate prompts. All candidates are evalu-
641 ated on the validation subset, and the variant with the highest macro F1 becomes the
642 starting point for the next round. This cycle continues until no further improvements
643 are observed for three consecutive iterations. Since [APO](#) refines only task instruc-
644 tions rather than model weights, it avoids the conventional risk of overfitting through
645 memorisation ([Y. Li, 2023](#)). To further ensure generalisability, we manually reviewed
646 the optimised prompt for signs of overfitting. For both critique and optimisation, we
647 employed GPT-5 ([OpenAI, 2025b](#)), as preliminary tests showed it to be substantially
648 more effective than smaller local alternatives such as Deepseek-R1 or Qwen. After
649 optimisation, all seven candidate models from the initial comparison were re-evaluated
650 with the final prompt, which is presented in Fig. [B4](#) in the appendix. We generated
651 a single optimised prompt rather than separate prompts for each model to derive a
652 generally applicable instruction set. In initial experiments, optimisation runs initiated
653 with Qwen3, GPT-4.1, and Llama3.1 all converged toward similar refinements. Given
654 this consistency and the substantial computational cost of per-model optimisation,
655 we implemented the full [APO](#) procedure only on one model.

656 To further test adaptability, the model/prompt combination was evaluated under
657 two configurations: zero-shot and few-shot learning. In the few-shot setting, we curated
658 four anonymised demonstration examples per disaster type, deliberately covering one
659 true positive, one true negative, one false positive, and one false negative observed
660 during the base prompt evaluation. All examples were modified with synthetic loca-
661 tions, timestamps, and language to prevent data leakage while preserving relevant
662 patterns. At inference time, the disaster-appropriate set of examples was dynamically
663 inserted into the prompt to reduce costs.

664 3.5 Multimodal integration

665 To assess the impact of combining multiple data modalities and analytical approaches,
666 we integrated the statistical and reasoning-based disaster detection methods into
667 a joint ensemble framework. Specifically, we merged the outputs from all statisti-
668 cal methods – social media hotspot detection, news hotspot detection, and weather
669 anomaly detection (c.f. [Sec. 3.3](#)) – with the predictions from the [LM](#)-based geospatial
670 reasoning methods (c.f. [Sec. 3.4](#)), covering both data retrieval strategies and zero-
671 shot/few-shot configurations. Since our classification task operates in an unsupervised

672 setting, we were only able to use training-free ensemble techniques, namely hard and
 673 soft voting (Dong, Yu, Cao, Shi, & Ma, 2020). In the hard voting setup, the predic-
 674 tion label is determined by a majority vote across all individual model outputs. In
 675 contrast, soft voting computes the sum of predicted probability scores for each class
 676 across models, and assigns the prediction label corresponding to the highest aggre-
 677 gated score. For both approaches, we also derived an overall ensemble probability
 678 score by averaging the individual model predictions.

679 To further disentangle the contributions of individual data sources and modalities,
 680 we conducted an ablation study focused on the LM-based approach. In the process,
 681 we systematically excluded individual input modalities, such as Bluesky social media,
 682 GDELT news or weather data, and compared the resulting performance to the full
 683 multimodal configuration.

684 3.6 Evaluation metrics

685 To evaluate the effectiveness of our disaster detection approach, we relied on class-
 686 balanced metrics to assess predictive performance in our binary classification setting.
 687 In addition, we measured the lead time of our detections relative to satellite-confirmed
 688 event presences.

689 3.6.1 Classification performance

690 As evident from Table 2, our data is severely class-imbalanced. Many traditional
 691 evaluation metrics, such as accuracy or Area Under the Receiver Operating Char-
 692 acteristic Curve (ROC-AUC) may therefore be misleading. For instance, in the
 693 Southern California wildfire case, a classifier that always predicts “no disaster” would
 694 achieve an accuracy of 97.56%, despite completely failing to detect any actual disaster
 695 occurrences. Therefore, we focused on the following evaluation metrics.

- 696 1. **Macro F1:** The macro F1 score is a class-balanced evaluation metric that rep-
 697 represents the harmonic mean of precision and recall, computed separately for each
 698 class and then averaged (simplified in Eq. 7). Due to its interpretability, macro F1
 699 was also the optimisation criterion for APO. The metric penalises large discrepan-
 700 cies between precision and recall and rewards a balanced trade-off between them
 701 (Rainio, Teuho, & Klén, 2024).

$$\text{M-F1} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2\text{TP}}{2\text{TP} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}} + \frac{2\text{TN}}{2\text{TN} + \text{FN} + \text{FP}} \right) \quad (7)$$

- 702 2. **Class-1 Recall:** Correctly identifying disaster-affected cells is critical, as respon-
 703 sive actions cannot be initiated otherwise (Sättele, Bründl, & Straub, 2016).
 704 Therefore, high recall (Powers, 2011) for class-1 (disaster presence) as depicted
 705 in Eq. 8 is desired. In operational settings, disaster detections are likely vali-
 706 dated against complementary data sources such as satellite imagery (Schmidt,
 707 Friedemann, et al., 2025; Wieland, Schmidt, Resch, Abecker, & Martinis, 2025).

$$\text{REC-1} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}} \quad (8)$$

708 3. **AUC-PR**: The **Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve (AUC-PR)** is a perfor-
709 mance metric for binary classification problems that is appropriate for rare events
710 (Davis & Goadrich, 2006; Sofaer, Hoeting, & Jarnevich, 2019). It quantifies the area
711 under the precision–recall curve obtained by varying a decision threshold τ over
712 the predicted class-1 probabilities. Higher **AUC-PR** values indicate better perfor-
713 mance, with the baseline being the positive class prevalence. The precision–recall
714 curve is constructed from the following relations:

$$\text{PREC-1} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}}, \quad \text{REC-1} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}} \quad (9)$$

715 The **AUC-PR** is then computed as:

$$\text{AUC-PR} = \int_0^1 \text{PREC-1}(\text{REC-1}) d\text{REC-1} \quad (10)$$

716 4. **MCC**: The **Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC)** (Eq. 11) is a balanced,
717 single-value measure that captures the correlation between predictions and labels,
718 considering both positive and negative classes (Matthews, 1975). In contrast to
719 macro F1, it also accounts for true negatives, and thereby penalises disaster pre-
720 dictions in unaffected areas in proportion to the total number of unaffected cells.
721 Accordingly, Chicco and Jurman (2020, 2023) argued that **MCC** is advantageous
722 over accuracy, F1 score and **ROC-AUC** because it incorporates all four components
723 of the confusion matrix. **MCC** ranges from $[-1, 1]$, with -1 and $+1$ representing
724 perfect misclassification and perfect classification. $\text{MCC} = 0$ is the expected value
725 for a random classifier.

$$\text{MCC} = \frac{(\text{TP} \cdot \text{TN}) - (\text{FP} \cdot \text{FN})}{\sqrt{(\text{TP} + \text{FP})(\text{TP} + \text{FN})(\text{TN} + \text{FP})(\text{TN} + \text{FN})}} \quad (11)$$

726 3.6.2 Early warning capabilities

727 Social media, news, and weather data are available in near real time and can therefore
728 support early warning (Schmidt, Friedemann, et al., 2025). To quantify the associated
729 early warning capabilities of our approach, we evaluated both the timeliness of detec-
730 tions relative to satellite data via lead times and the ability to detect initial disaster
731 onset via the first-occurrence detection rate.

732 1. **True Positive Lead Time**: For each H3 cell c , where a disaster was successfully
733 detected (true positive), we define the lead time (in days) as in Eq. 12. $t_{\text{event}}^{(c)}$ denotes
734 the first occurrence of a flood or wildfire in cell c , and $t_{\text{first prediction}}^{(c)}$ is the first time
735 our method predicted a disaster in that cell prior to or at the event time.

$$\Delta t_c = t_{\text{event}}^{(c)} - t_{\text{first prediction}}^{(c)}, \quad (12)$$

736 To avoid disproportionate influence of predictions made far in advance of the
737 actual event, lead times were evaluated within a fixed maximum horizon τ_{max} .
738 In our case, we set $\tau_{\text{max}} = 5$, as both the flood and wildfire events evolved over
739 relatively short time periods of only a few days (Maskell, 2024; US EPA, 2025).

740 Based on $\Delta t_c \in \{1, \dots, N^{(\text{TP})}\}$ for each cell that contained at least one true
 741 positive detection and τ_{\max} , we subsequently define the lead-time curve as in Eq. 13.
 742 $D(\tau)$ represents the fraction of disaster events detected at least τ days in advance.

$$D(\tau) = \frac{1}{N^{(\text{TP})}} \sum_{c=1}^{N^{(\text{TP})}} \mathbb{1}(\Delta t_c \geq \tau), \quad \tau \in \{1, 2, \dots, \tau_{\max}\}, \quad (13)$$

743 Mathematically, $D(t)$ can be viewed as the survival function of a random vari-
 744 able Δt , which represents the lead time across all cells, i.e. $D(\tau) = \mathbb{P}[\Delta t \geq \tau]$. The
 745 discrete sum of this curve, over the interval $[1, \tau_{\max}]$ approximates the expected
 746 lead time $\mathbb{E}[\Delta t]$ (Grinstead & Snell, 1998). For readability, we call this the **True**
 747 **Positive Lead Time (TP-LT)**, which can be expressed as in Eq. 14.

$$\text{TP-LT} = \sum_{\tau=1}^{\tau_{\max}} D(\tau) \quad (14)$$

748 2. **First-Occurrence Detection Rate:** To evaluate whether the initial disaster
 749 onset was correctly identified, we redefined the cell labels such that only the first
 750 occurrence of a disaster in each cell is considered a positive instance, while all sub-
 751 sequent time steps were treated as negatives. Under this relabelling, we computed
 752 recall (Powers, 2011) as in Eq. 15, which translates to the **First-Occurrence Detec-**
 753 **tion Rate (FODR)**. The metric isolates the model’s ability to detect the onset of
 754 events, independent of subsequent detections.

$$\text{FODR} = \text{REC}_{\text{first}} = \frac{\text{TP}_{\text{first}}}{\text{TP}_{\text{first}} + \text{FN}_{\text{first}}} \quad (15)$$

755 4 Results

756 This section first investigates our statistical event detection approaches across data
 757 sources. Subsequently, it presents the results of our geospatial reasoning approaches.
 758 Lastly, it describes performance differences when combining different methods and
 759 data sources.

760 4.1 Statistical event detection

761 Table 3 summarises the performance of the statistical event detection methods for
 762 each data source based on class-1 recall, macro F1 (M-F1), **AUC-PR**, and **MCC**.
 763 Furthermore, it depicts the **TP-LT** and **FODR** as auxiliary measures of timeliness.

764 For the 2024 Central Europe floods, Getis-Ord G_i^* hotspot detection based on
 765 **GDELT** news headlines achieved the highest overall performance, with an macro F1
 766 of 0.58, an **AUC-PR** of 0.24, and an **MCC** of 0.20. The method using geoparsed Bluesky
 767 posts reached a slightly higher class-1 recall of 0.18 and an equal macro F1 of 0.58,
 768 but lower **AUC-PR** (0.16) and **MCC** (0.18). The weather anomaly detection approach
 769 showed the lowest performance, with a lower macro F1 of 0.47, an **AUC-PR** of 0.11, and
 770 a negative **MCC** (−0.04), indicating poor agreement with the satellite-based reference
 771 data.

772 For the 2025 Southern California wildfires, both G_i^* hotspot detection methods
773 based on **GDELT** and Bluesky data achieved the highest class-1 recall of 0.47, demon-
774 strating their ability to identify a subset of affected cells. The respective macro F1
775 scores were 0.56 (**GDELT**) and 0.55 (Bluesky), though precision remained low, result-
776 ing in small **AUC-PR** values of 0.07 and 0.06. The corresponding **MCC** values (0.19
777 and 0.18) suggest weak but positive correlation between predictions and actual disas-
778 ter occurrences. The weather anomaly detection method again failed to identify any
779 disaster-affected cells (REC-1: 0.00), resulting in a macro F1 of 0.49, an **AUC-PR**
780 of 0.02, and an **MCC** of 0.00, equivalent to random performance.

781 In terms of early warning capabilities, weather anomaly detection produced the
782 earliest signals (**TP-LT**: 3.71 days) for the 2024 Central Europe floods, but only mod-
783 erate **FODR** (0.39). G_i^* on geoparsed Bluesky data detected fewer first occurrences
784 (**FODR**: 0.16) but relatively early (**TP-LT**: 3.06 days). The equivalent hotspot detec-
785 tion on **GDELT** news headlines identified more first occurrences (**FODR**: 0.29) but at
786 a later point in time (**TP-LT**: 1.54 days). For the 2025 Southern California wildfires,
787 both G_i^* approaches achieved high **TP-LT** (3.18 to 3.40 days) and **FODR** (0.40). The
788 weather anomaly detection method failed to provide any early warning capabilities
789 (**TP-LT**: 0.00 days, **FODR**: 0.00).

Table 3 Performance of our statistical event detection methods across
2024 Central Europe floods and the 2025 Southern California wildfires. The best
scores are marked in bold. **TP-LT** and **FODR** are reported as auxiliary metrics
of timeliness and should not be interpreted in isolation.

Use case	Approach	Classification performance				Timeliness	
		REC-1	M-F1	MCC	AUC-PR	TP-LT	FODR
Floods	G_i^* (Bsky)	0.18	0.58	0.18	0.16	3.06	0.16
	G_i^* (GDELT)	0.16	0.58	0.20	0.24	1.54	0.29
	Weather	0.17	0.47	-0.04	0.11	3.71	0.39
Wildfires	G_i^* (Bsky)	0.47	0.55	0.18	0.06	3.40	0.40
	G_i^* (GDELT)	0.47	0.56	0.19	0.07	3.18	0.40
	Weather	0.00	0.49	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00

790 4.2 Geospatial reasoning

791 For our geospatial reasoning approach, we first briefly present the results of our model
792 selection and prompt validation process. We then report the evaluation metrics of our
793 final configuration on the full datasets.

794 4.2.1 Validation

795 Table 4 summarises the macro F1 score, invalid (non-parsable) **JSON** outputs, and
796 sample latency across all considered **LMs** before and after **APO**. Each value is aver-
797 aged over ten runs and across both use cases, with the stratified 10% validation subset

798 as a basis for evaluation. Before applying [APO](#), we evaluated different values of n (the
799 number of injected social media posts and news headlines). Macro F1 scores stabilised
800 beyond $n \geq 10$. Therefore, this value was used in all subsequent experiments. Among
801 the tested models, Qwen3:8B was selected for [APO](#) due to its high computational effi-
802 ciency and because it performed on par with Qwen3:14B in early experimental runs,
803 suggesting strong potential for improvement. After [APO](#), we observed generally similar
804 macro F1 scores across most models, with values ranging from 0.50 to 0.58. One excep-
805 tion was Llama3.1:8B, which consistently exhibited low classification performance and
806 produced a substantial number of non-parsable outputs. The Deepseek-R1 models
807 failed to produce any valid outputs due to persistent infinite reasoning loops, where
808 the models repeatedly generated reasoning tokens without terminating in a response.
809 For the full-scale evaluation, we eventually selected Qwen3:14B with the optimised
810 prompt and $n = 10$, as it offered the overall best performance among open-weight
811 models, and the second-fastest inference speed.

Table 4 Average performance across both use cases for different [LMs](#) using the human-engineered versus the machine-optimised system prompts on our stratified 10% validation subset. All results are the mean values over 10 runs, and the standard deviation is depicted in brackets. “Invalid” refers to the absolute (average) number of non-parsable [JSON](#) outputs. The best scores are marked in bold, the second-best scores are underlined.

Model	Base prompt			Optimised prompt		
	M-F1	Invalid	Latency	M-F1	Invalid	Latency
GPT-4.1-nano	0.41 (± 0.01)	0.00 (± 0.00)	1.04s (± 0.09)	0.50 (± 0.02)	0.00 (± 0.00)	1.35s (± 0.96)
GPT-5-nano	0.60 (± 0.02)	0.00 (± 0.00)	9.87s (± 1.13)	0.58 (± 0.03)	0.00 (± 0.00)	17.55s (± 0.92)
Gemma3:12B	0.52 (± 0.01)	<u>23.90</u> (± 0.57)	0.92s (± 0.02)	0.54 (± 0.01)	0.00 (± 0.00)	1.36s (± 0.03)
Llama3.1:8B	0.30 (± 0.17)	97.38 (± 1.21)	1.75s (± 0.01)	0.30 (± 0.02)	<u>23.10</u> (± 2.35)	3.17s (± 0.05)
Qwen3:8B	0.49 (± 0.00)	0.00 (± 0.00)	0.47s (± 0.00)	0.55 (± 0.01)	0.00 (± 0.00)	0.56s (± 0.00)
Qwen3:14B	<u>0.56</u> (± 0.00)	0.00 (± 0.00)	<u>0.73s</u> (± 0.01)	<u>0.56</u> (± 0.00)	0.00 (± 0.00)	<u>0.81s</u> (± 0.01)
Deepseek-R1:8B			<i>infinite thought loop, no output</i>			
Deepseek-R1:14B			<i>infinite thought loop, no output</i>			

812 4.2.2 Full-scale evaluation

813 Table 5 presents the performance of [LM](#)-based event detection with Qwen3:14B
814 across our full H3 evaluation grids, comparing zero-shot and few-shot configurations
815 combined with cell-based and score-based data retrieval strategies.

816 For the 2024 Central Europe floods, the zero-shot learning configuration with
817 score-based retrieval achieved the most balanced performance, reaching a class-1 recall
818 of 0.34, a macro F1 of 0.65, a [MCC](#) of 0.30, and an [AUC-PR](#) of 0.30. This corresponds
819 to a substantial improvement compared to the statistical baselines. The few-shot cell-
820 based variant performed comparably, with a class-1 recall of 0.33, a macro F1 of 0.64,
821 a [MCC](#) of 0.27, and an [AUC-PR](#) of 0.25. While the few-shot score-based configuration

822 achieved the highest class-1 recall (0.63), indicating strong sensitivity to disaster-
 823 affected cells, its macro F1 (0.56), **MCC** (0.23), and **AUC-PR** (0.26) were slightly
 824 lower, suggesting a higher false-positive rate. The zero-shot cell-based setup achieved
 825 moderate results (REC-1: 0.15, M-F1: 0.58, **MCC**: 0.20, **AUC-PR**: 0.22).

826 Conversely, the zero-shot learning configuration with cell-based retrieval achieved
 827 the most balanced metrics for the 2025 Southern California wildfires, with a class-1
 828 recall of 0.30, a macro F1 of 0.63, a **MCC** of 0.26, and an **AUC-PR** of 0.24. The few-shot
 829 cell-based setup achieved a higher class-1 recall of 0.57, macro F1 of 0.57, a competitive
 830 **MCC** of 0.23, and an **AUC-PR** of 0.16. The few-shot score-based configuration reached
 831 the highest class-1 recall (0.80) but at the cost of reduced balance and precision,
 832 reflected in its lower macro F1 (0.42), **MCC** (0.12), and **AUC-PR** (0.10). The zero-shot
 833 score-based configuration achieved moderate values across all metrics (REC-1: 0.40,
 834 M-F1: 0.58, **MCC**: 0.20, **AUC-PR**: 0.15).

835 Regarding prediction timeliness, the few-shot score-based configuration achieved
 836 the strongest early warning capabilities for the 2024 Central Europe floods, with a
 837 **TP-LT** of 3.67 days and an **FODR** of 0.95, indicating both timely detection and a high
 838 proportion of first occurrences identified. The few-shot cell-based variant performed
 839 moderately, detecting fewer first occurrences (**FODR**: 0.50) but still providing rela-
 840 tively early signals (**TP-LT**: 1.97 days). The zero-shot score-based approach delivered
 841 comparable early warning performance (**TP-LT**: 1.94 days, **FODR**: 0.55), while the
 842 zero-shot cell-based setup provided the weakest early warning capabilities (**TP-LT**:
 843 1.59 days, **FODR**: 0.32). Likewise, the few-shot score-based approach achieved the
 844 highest **TP-LT** (4.00 days) and **FODR** (0.73), for the 2025 Southern California wild-
 845 fires, followed by the few-shot cell-based variant (**TP-LT**: 2.40 days, **FODR**: 0.53). The
 846 zero-shot score-based configuration also achieved notable early warning performance
 847 for wildfires, with a **TP-LT** of 3.13 days and an **FODR** of 0.27, while the zero-shot
 848 cell-based setup did not provide significant early warning capabilities (**TP-LT**: 0.00
 849 days, **FODR**: 0.20), though it achieved the highest general classification performance.

Table 5 Performance of LM-based event detection variants with Qwen:14B after APO across 2024 Central Europe floods and the 2025 Southern California wildfires. The best scores are marked in bold. **TP-LT** and **FODR** are reported as auxiliary metrics of timeliness and should not be interpreted in isolation.

Use case	Variant	Retrieval	Classification performance				Timeliness	
			REC-1	M-F1	MCC	AUC-PR	TP-LT	FODR
Floods	Zero-shot	Cells	0.15	0.58	0.20	0.22	1.59	0.32
	Zero-shot	Score	0.34	0.65	0.30	0.30	1.94	0.55
	Few-shot	Cells	0.33	0.64	0.27	0.25	1.97	0.50
	Few-shot	Score	0.63	0.56	0.23	0.26	3.66	0.95
Wildfires	Zero-shot	Cells	0.30	0.63	0.26	0.24	0.00	0.20
	Zero-shot	Score	0.40	0.58	0.20	0.15	3.13	0.27
	Few-shot	Cells	0.57	0.57	0.23	0.16	2.40	0.53
	Few-shot	Score	0.80	0.42	0.12	0.10	4.00	0.73

4.3 Multimodal integration

Table 6 presents the results of our multimodal integration experiments, comparing statistical ensembles (hard or soft voting) with their LM-based counterparts and corresponding ablation variants. We primarily focus on balanced classification metrics (macro F1, MCC, and AUC-PR), as they provide the most robust assessment of model performance. Accordingly, we refer to the best-performing configurations as those achieving the highest values across these metrics.

For the statistical approaches, only the best-performing ensemble type per configuration is reported: soft voting for the 2024 Central Europe floods and hard voting for the 2025 Southern California wildfires. For the LM-based approach, we used the variant that achieved the highest overall performance in Sec. 4.2.2: zero-shot learning with score-based retrieval for the 2024 Central Europe floods and zero-shot learning with cell-based retrieval for the 2025 Southern California wildfires. Across both disaster cases, multimodal integration consistently improved event detection compared to single-source methods.

For the 2024 Central Europe floods, the LM-based configuration combining Bluesky, GDELT, and weather data achieved high performance with macro F1 of 0.65, an MCC of 0.30, and an AUC-PR of 0.29, outperforming the equivalent statistical ensemble (M-F1: 0.61, MCC: 0.22, AUC-PR: 0.25). Ablation results show that removing one modality caused only minor changes in overall performance. The GDELT-weather and Bluesky-GDELT combinations both maintained stable macro F1 scores (0.62–0.65) and MCC values (0.30–0.35), suggesting that these sources capture complementary event signals. In contrast, weather alone yielded the weakest results for both the statistical baseline and the LM-based equivalent (MCC: ≈ 0.00 , M-F1: 0.47). The GDELT-only configuration with geospatial reasoning reached the highest single-source AUC-PR and MCC values of 0.35 and 0.30, respectively.

For the 2025 Southern California wildfires, similar patterns were observed. The LM-based multimodal configuration achieved high overall scores (M-F1: 0.63, MCC: 0.26, AUC-PR: 0.26), again surpassing the statistical ensemble baseline (M-F1: 0.58, MCC: 0.18, AUC-PR: 0.11). Ablation results indicate that excluding weather data generally had little effect, whereas excluding GDELT led to noticeable drops in both macro F1 and MCC. The LM-based configuration using Bluesky and GDELT achieved the best ablation performance (M-F1: 0.67, MCC: 0.34, AUC-PR: 0.22), outperforming all other partial configurations. Single-source setups again yielded notably lower scores, particularly for weather data (M-F1: 0.49, AUC-PR: 0.02–0.03, MCC: 0.00).

To assess the effects of combining statistical and LM-based methods, we evaluated all method combinations from Sec. 4.1 and Sec. 4.2.2 using hard and soft voting. Fig. 4 summarises the results. The boxplots on the left show the distributions of class-1 recall, macro F1, MCC, and AUC-PR across all ensemble configurations and both use cases. While class-1 recall exhibited the greatest variability, macro F1 and MCC remained within narrower ranges. No ensemble configuration clearly outperformed the best single model, although several achieved comparable macro F1 and MCC values, indicating balanced prediction quality. The scatter plot on the right relates ensemble size (1–7 models) to macro F1, showing that performance variability decreased as more

Table 6 Evaluation metrics for the two use cases across statistical ensembles and the corresponding LM-based zero-shot learning variants with ablation. For the statistical ensembles, only the best-performing method (hard or soft) is displayed. The best scores per row are highlighted in bold.

Use case	Bsky	GDELT	Weather	Statistical			LM		
				M-F1	MCC	AUC-PR	M-F1	MCC	AUC-PR
Floods	✓	✓	✓	0.61	0.22	0.25	0.65	0.30	0.30
	✗	✓	✓	0.58	0.17	0.23	0.63	0.30	0.29
	✓	✗	✓	0.58	0.17	0.23	0.63	0.29	0.25
	✓	✓	✗	0.63	0.26	0.27	0.66	0.33	0.30
	✗	✗	✓	0.47	-0.04	0.11	0.47	0.00	0.12
	✗	✓	✗	0.58	0.20	0.24	0.65	0.35	0.35
Wildfires	✓	✓	✓	0.58	0.18	0.11	0.63	0.26	0.24
	✗	✓	✓	0.57	0.17	0.11	0.65	0.33	0.19
	✓	✗	✓	0.57	0.17	0.11	0.62	0.23	0.15
	✓	✓	✗	0.56	0.16	0.11	0.63	0.26	0.20
	✗	✗	✓	0.49	0.00	0.02	0.49	0.00	0.03
	✗	✓	✗	0.56	0.19	0.07	0.67	0.34	0.22
	✓	✗	✗	0.55	0.18	0.06	0.60	0.21	0.15

895 models were combined, but with a slight decline in maximum macro F1 score for larger
 896 ensembles. Large ensembles may therefore dilute the contribution of well-performing
 897 individual models.

Fig. 4 Left: Performance distribution of all possible ensembles of methods, compared against the best single method. Right: Macro F1 scores for all ensembles, categorised by the number of involved models.

898 4.4 Case study

899 Fig. 5 qualitatively compares spatial prediction outcomes between the full multimodal
900 LM-based and statistical ensemble methods for both disaster cases. For the 2024 Cen-
901 tral Europe floods, the LM-based zero-shot approach (top) detected a cluster of true
902 positives along the Danube corridor, particularly around Vienna and Linz, with a few
903 false positives in peripheral regions. The statistical ensemble (bottom) also captured
904 the main affected area but produced a more dispersed pattern, including numerous
905 false predictions between the Danube and Prague. For the 2025 Southern Califor-
906 nia wildfires, both methods correctly identified the Los Angeles region as the main
907 hotspot. The LM-based approach (top) detected wildfires in more dispersed regions,
908 while for the statistical ensemble, all positives were concentrated around Los Angeles.

909 True positives generally correspond to grid cells where external evidence, such
910 as Bluesky posts or news reports, explicitly confirmed the occurrence of a flood or
911 wildfire. False positives, in contrast, often resulted from limitations in geoparsing,
912 particularly when locations were mapped to coarse or ambiguous geographic refer-
913 ences. This effect is visible in the Central Europe floods case as a prediction near the
914 centroid of “Austria” (close to Salzburg), and in the Southern California wildfire case
915 near the centroid of “Riverside County”. False negatives primarily occurred in areas
916 with sparse or missing input data, where few or no geoparsed social media posts or
917 news articles were available to support a correct prediction. In all cases, weather data
918 alone provided insufficient information to make a clear prediction.

Fig. 5 Qualitative comparison of spatial predictions from the LM-based zero-shot approach and the full multimodal statistical ensemble for the 2024 Central Europe floods and the 2025 Southern California wildfires. The boxes show the LM-based summaries generated during inference, along with post/article counts and weather statistics used in the statistical approach.

919 **5 Discussion**

920 We first discuss our results and subsequently critically reflect on the methodology of
 921 our study.

922 **5.1 Discussion of the results**

923 Our findings provide a comprehensive picture of how statistical and LM-based
 924 approaches perform for detecting disaster events from social media, news and weather
 925 data. Yet, many aspects remain subject to discussion.

926 *Statistical event detection*

927 Overall, Bluesky posts and geo-referenced GDELT headlines provided limited yet
928 measurable signals for statistical anomaly detection. Spatial hotspot detection with
929 Getis-Ord G_i^* achieved moderate performance, with GDELT slightly outperforming
930 Bluesky in both disaster scenarios. This pattern indicates that news reports offer more
931 consistent spatial cues than user-generated social media content, as they typically refer-
932 ence affected locations systematically, whereas social media posts often include no
933 or only informal location mentions (Serere, Resch, & Havas, 2023). Sensitivity gener-
934 ally remained low. For the 2024 Central Europe floods, class-1 recall reached values up
935 to 0.16–0.18, and for the 2025 Southern California wildfires, scores ranged up to 0.47.
936 This indicates that only a small subset of affected grid cells was identified. The higher
937 recall values for wildfires can likely be attributed to the clear spatial concentration
938 of fire activity around Los Angeles (US EPA, 2025), combined with higher posting
939 activity in the USA (Semrush, 2025). The overall macro F1 scores (0.55–0.58) were
940 comparable to those reported by Schmidt, Friedemann, et al. (2025) for Twitter, sug-
941 gesting that Bluesky and GDELT provide similar value for statistical event detection.
942 Weather anomaly detection performed poorly in both use cases, with near-random
943 performance metrics (macro F1: 0.47–0.49, MCC: ≈ 0.00). This can be traced back
944 to several factors. For the floods, elevated precipitation led to a few true positives,
945 but precipitation alone was not always indicative of flooding, and heavy rainfall in
946 upstream catchments can trigger flooding downstream. The location of rainfall anom-
947 alies does therefore not necessarily coincide with the location of inundation. For the
948 wildfires, no meaningful weather anomalies were observed, since the disaster occurred
949 in January during normal temperatures without any notable weather characteristics
950 except dryness.

951 *Geospatial reasoning*

952 Our geospatial reasoning experiments demonstrate that LMs can effectively detect
953 disasters from heterogeneous contextual evidence, even in zero-shot settings. With
954 only ten or fewer social media posts and news headlines per prompt, our LM approach
955 outperformed all statistical baseline methods and ensemble variants.

956 Across models, APO overall improved validation performance, yielding an average
957 macro F1 increase of 5.3%. APO also substantially reduced invalid JSON outputs,
958 particularly for Llama and Gemini. Smaller models benefited the most from optimi-
959 sation, which is consistent with Luo, Liu, and Esping (2023). In contrast, the effect
960 of APO on larger reasoning-capable models such as GPT-5-nano and Qwen3:14B was
961 limited or slightly negative, likely because these models already produced coherent
962 outputs under the base prompt. These findings suggest that a well-designed human
963 prompt combined with a strong reasoning model can already yield near-optimal per-
964 formance, making APO less useful in such settings. This ties in with the findings of
965 G. Wang et al. (2025). In retrospect, focusing on APO would likely not have been nec-
966 essary, as the impact was marginal for our final configuration. However, it would be
967 valuable to investigate how different critique models influence optimisation outcomes,
968 and to explore per-model optimisation strategies, to better understand how various
969 LMs approach geospatial reasoning tasks.

970 In terms of the tested models, the GPT and Qwen3 variants consistently achieved
971 the highest performance metrics, aligning with findings by [Hanny, Schmidt, Gandhi,
972 and Resch \(2025\)](#). Deepseek-R1 consistently failed to terminate during reasoning,
973 indicating unstable internal thought processes for its smaller variants. The compari-
974 son between data retrieval strategies revealed that score-based retrieval worked best
975 for the 2024 Central Europe floods, while cell-based retrieval was more effective for
976 the 2025 Southern California wildfires. This likely reflects differences in spatial struc-
977 ture between the two events. Flooded areas in Europe were geographically dispersed,
978 and incorporating spatially and temporally close information from neighbouring cells
979 therefore improved contextual understanding. In contrast, the wildfires use case was
980 concentrated around the Los Angeles region. Expanding data retrieval to neighbour-
981 hood areas potentially introduced noise from unrelated areas. Quantitatively, the
982 score-based retrieval method obtained an average of 10 content items from both
983 Bluesky and [GDELT](#) per cell, compared to only 1.35 Bluesky posts and 0.5 news
984 headlines for cell-based retrieval. These results suggest that retrieval strategies must
985 be adapted to the spatial structure of disasters, and that a fixed configuration is not
986 always optimal.

987 During prompt construction, we also observed that including reverse-geocoded
988 place names in the user prompt improved our evaluation metrics by several per-
989 centage points, indicating that [LMs](#) interpret geographic text more effectively than
990 numerical coordinates. This is consistent with [Ji et al. \(2025\)](#). Few-shot learning
991 using anonymised demonstration examples increased class-1 recall but slightly reduced
992 macro F1 and [MCC](#), suggesting that while the demonstrations improved sensitivity
993 to disaster occurrences, they also led to more false positives due to overemphasis on
994 disaster-related cues.

995 *Multimodal integration*

996 The multimodal integration experiments further demonstrated the advantage of [LMs](#)
997 over statistical ensembles when reasoning across heterogeneous data sources. For
998 both disaster use cases, [LM](#)-based reasoning across multiple data modalities achieved
999 top scores, surpassing all statistical variants. In some instances, single-source event
1000 detection yielded comparable or higher performance metrics than for the multimodal
1001 configurations, particularly using [GDELT](#). For the wildfires use case, this can be
1002 attributed to the spatial concentration of wildfire-related news reports in Los Ange-
1003 les, where media coverage closely aligned with the active wildfires. For the floods use
1004 case, such a single-source setup involved a trade-off in the form of lower class-1 recall.

1005 Qualitatively, the [LM](#)-based predictions produced fewer false positives for the
1006 floods and broader spatial coverage around the Los Angeles hotspot for the wildfires,
1007 whereas the statistical methods generated more dispersed flood predictions and more
1008 concentrated wildfire detections. These results suggest that [LMs](#) can integrate het-
1009 erogeneous evidence more effectively, and produce more coherent and geographically
1010 plausible disaster patterns than statistical event detection methods, which tend to be
1011 sensitive to local hotspots or noise.

1012 *Early warning capabilities*

1013 Both the statistical and LM-based disaster detection approaches exhibited meaning-
1014 ful early warning capabilities, with consistently positive TP-LT values across most
1015 configurations. The LM-based approach with few-shot score-based retrieval was par-
1016 ticularly effective, achieving TP-LT values of 3.5 to 4 days and FODR of 0.73 to
1017 0.95. However, higher TP-LT values were generally associated with reduced overall
1018 classification performance and higher false positive rates. This can be attributed to
1019 increased sensitivity to disaster-related signals due to the few-shot examples. Addi-
1020 tionally, all early warning metrics are inherently biased by the temporal granularity
1021 of the available satellite reference data. For the Central Europe flood scenario, satel-
1022 lite observations for each cell were only available every 1 to 3 days, whereas for the
1023 Southern California wildfires, new satellite data were available at least twice a day.
1024 Lead times should therefore be interpreted with this limitation in mind.

1025 *Practical value*

1026 For disaster response operations, our methodology suggests two distinct applications.
1027 High-recall, high-lead-time setups can be useful for generating early alerts and direct-
1028 ing satellites to potential disaster areas, as demonstrated by Schmidt, Friedemann, et
1029 al. (2025). More balanced and overall precise configurations are suitable for continu-
1030 ous monitoring, like implemented in the GDACS by Stollberg and de Groeve (2012),
1031 where reliable and consistent detection of affected disaster regions across very large
1032 regions is required. In such setups, our approach can provide a large-scale and cross-
1033 border big picture, which is often missing in traditional response efforts. Even when
1034 the occurrence of a disaster is already known, the precise location of hotspots and
1035 their temporal evolution frequently remain unclear and fragmented across local and
1036 regional scales (S.E. Chang & Tanner, 2022). In this context, our LM-based method
1037 can also be leveraged to generate targeted summaries of social media or news activity
1038 in affected areas, reducing information overload for disaster managers.

1039 *Other considerations*

1040 It is also important to acknowledge that all evaluation metrics are affected by a degree
1041 of uncertainty in the satellite-derived reference data. The delineation of flooded areas
1042 or active wildfires may include false positives or negatives, and our threshold-based
1043 approach for defining event presence introduced additional ambiguity. In addition, the
1044 reference data represents only the hazard extent – the physical footprint of floods or
1045 wildfires – rather than the disaster extent, which depends on exposure and impact.
1046 For the events analysed here, we consider hazard extent a reasonable proxy for dis-
1047 aster extent, since both occurred in densely populated, infrastructure-rich regions.
1048 We furthermore verified the plausibility of the derived disaster extent against official
1049 reports. Besides that, there is a high likelihood of false negatives in sparsely popu-
1050 lated areas where hazards occurred but generated little to no social or media activity.
1051 Consequently, evaluation metrics close to 1 are unrealistic and not expected. As illus-
1052 trated in Fig. 5, false positives often occurred in sparsely populated areas, where
1053 social media and news activity were limited and the potential damage extent was

1054 comparatively low. Future work could therefore refine the evaluation by incorporating
1055 population-weighting mechanisms.

1056 Lastly, practical constraints also remain. While LMs demonstrated strong rea-
1057 soning capabilities, their high computational cost and inference time currently limit
1058 scalability and real-time applicability. These limitations are expected to decrease
1059 as model efficiency improves through ongoing advances in architecture design and
1060 optimisation techniques (Jolicoeur-Martineau, 2025).

1061 5.2 Discussion of the methodology

1062 Our methodology faces several limitations related to the quality of the available data
1063 and spatial information, as well as the design of our analytical framework.

1064 *Data quality*

1065 First of all, data collection for Bluesky was limited to keyword-based queries with
1066 an API that lacked a functional pagination mechanism at the time of data collection
1067 (bluesky-social GitHub, 2024). Consequently, it is impossible to guarantee the com-
1068 pleteness of the retrieved posts, especially since data retrieval is largely dependent
1069 on the selected keywords. The keyword-based search also makes it hard to estimate
1070 overall platform activity, which reduces the reliability of relative measures such as the
1071 ratio of disaster-related posts to the total number of retrieved posts, as used in previ-
1072 ous work. Nonetheless, this share still correlated well with the temporal progression of
1073 the events. A further constraint is the demographic and geographic bias of the Bluesky
1074 platform. The user base is strongly skewed towards the USA (Semrush, 2025), which
1075 likely limits data quantity and quality for the 2024 Central Europe floods. More-
1076 over, although Bluesky shares similarities with Twitter and has attracted migrating
1077 users (Shekhar, Papalexakis, Gao, Jiang, & Riionato, 2024), it remains comparatively
1078 underexplored (Failla & Rossetti, 2024). Future work might therefore integrate addi-
1079 tional social media data sources to improve representativeness (e.g. Vračević et al.,
1080 2025). In this context, automated LM-based querying strategies could help mitigate
1081 biases introduced by manual keyword selection.

1082 Simultaneously, the retrieved Bluesky posts required geoparsing to extract mean-
1083 ingful location information. We used the Irchel Geoparser by Gomes (2024) to realise
1084 this, as it is highly scalable and includes a context-aware toponym disambigua-
1085 tion mechanism, which has proven to be much more accurate compared to previous
1086 approaches (e.g. Serere et al., 2023). However, the method relies on the GeoNames
1087 gazetteer (GeoNames, n.d.), which only includes coarse place names like countries,
1088 cities or villages. Since location mentions in social media texts are typically coarse to
1089 start with (Hu et al., 2023), the spatial resolution of our geoparsed Bluesky dataset
1090 remains low. This significantly limits and effectively upper bounds the performance of
1091 our methodology (c.f. Fig. 5). Future work should examine whether more fine-grained
1092 geoparsing is feasible for Bluesky data and whether distinctions between in-situ and
1093 remote location mentions (Serere & Resch, 2025) can be integrated into the workflow.

1094 GDELT news data also presents several data quality limitations. Only the
1095 headlines can be retrieved from the GKG, meaning that our classification of disaster-
1096 relatedness is based solely on headline content. Furthermore, geographic locations

1097 are extracted using a gazetteer-based approach implemented by the [GDELT](#) project
1098 ([Saz-Carranza, Maturana, & Quer, n.d.](#)). This results in relatively coarse spatial res-
1099 olution, leading to similar methodological limitations as for the Bluesky data. Future
1100 work should also explore using complete news articles for event detection. However,
1101 this comes with several technical challenges, as news data is often subject to paywalls
1102 and the websites themselves often differ substantially. Additionally, weather data from
1103 Meteostat was not always available from exactly the same station for each H3 grid
1104 cell at each point in time. We therefore expect minor inconsistencies in where exactly
1105 the weather was recorded. However, this did not influence the overall coherence of the
1106 data during manual inspection.

1107 More generally, both social media and news data are biased towards larger, high-
1108 impact events, which are more likely to be reported and discussed ([Theja Bhavaraju,
1109 Beyney, & Nicholson, 2019](#)). Smaller-scale disasters may therefore be underrepresented
1110 or entirely missed. In this study, we deliberately focused on large-scale events to
1111 ensure sufficient data coverage for quantitative evaluation. Future work should assess
1112 the robustness of the proposed methodology across disasters of varying spatial and
1113 temporal scales.

1114 *Evaluation framework*

1115 Our grid-based evaluation framework represents a key methodological contribution,
1116 as it enables the quantitative assessment of disaster detection accuracy. However,
1117 it is also affected by the [Modifiable Areal Unit Problem \(MAUP\)](#) ([Fotheringham
1118 & Wong, 1991](#)). During the conceptualisation phase of our method, we evaluated
1119 H3 resolutions 3, 4, and 5, with edge lengths of approximately 68.98 km, 26.07 km,
1120 9.85 km, respectively. For resolution 3, macro F1 scores were slightly higher than for
1121 resolution 4 under the same setup. However, the large spatial units make it ambiguous
1122 to define disaster occurrence and hard to pinpoint it to specific areas, limiting the
1123 usefulness of the results. In contrast, resolution 5 led to a substantial performance drop
1124 (macro F1: ≈ 0.1 to 0.2), as the spatial granularity exceeded the effective resolution
1125 of our geoparsed Bluesky and [GDELT](#) data, resulting in severe data sparsity. We
1126 eventually selected H3 resolution 4 cells, which have a maximum diameter of 52.14 km
1127 and adequately capture the spatial extent of most local disasters ([de Albuquerque
1128 et al., 2015](#); [Sakaki et al., 2010](#); [Schmidt, Friedemann, et al., 2025](#)), while remaining
1129 coarse enough to ensure adequate data availability per cell. Exploring hierarchical or
1130 multi-resolution approaches – for example, by combining fine-grained cells in data-
1131 rich areas with coarser cells in sparse regions – represents a promising direction for
1132 future work to reduce sensitivity to this design choice.

1133 The [MAUP](#) is especially problematic for the statistical disaster detection
1134 approaches, as it relies entirely on the grid. In our [LM](#)-based approach, we tried to
1135 circumvent the issue using our score-based data retrieval strategy, which is based on
1136 distances instead of fixed cells. This allows the method to be applied more flexibly to
1137 specific locations, such as cities, without being constrained by grid boundaries. Future
1138 work should aim to reduce the dependence on fixed grid structures while preserving
1139 capabilities for quantitative evaluation. In parallel, our statistical approaches depend
1140 on fixed threshold values. Even though these have been proven effective in previous

1141 studies (e.g. Schmidt, Friedemann, et al., 2025), follow-up research should investigate
1142 more adaptive approaches for choosing these hyperparameters.

1143 *Geospatial reasoning*

1144 Regarding our geospatial reasoning approach, model size and inference time remain
1145 major limitations. To ensure real-time applicability, we deliberately focused on **SLMs**
1146 in our methodology, keeping inference times under one second per cell and day. How-
1147 ever, we initially also evaluated larger **FMs** like Qwen3:32B or Llama3:70B. In these
1148 preliminary experiments, larger models did not consistently yield better results than
1149 their smaller counterparts, and in the case of Qwen3:32B, even led to lower macro F1
1150 scores than Qwen3:8B. These results indicate that **Large Language Models (LLMs)**
1151 are not necessarily more powerful than **SLMs** for specialised inference tasks, which
1152 has also been argued by Belcak et al. (2025).

1153 The spatiotemporal structure of our H3 grid data also posed challenges for model
1154 and prompt validation. A conventional validation/test split risked excluding specific
1155 regions or time periods, which could distort overall results. To mitigate this, we
1156 applied **APO** on a subset of the evaluation data. While this approach is less robust
1157 than validation with a separate hold-out set, overfitting is generally not a major con-
1158 cern for zero-shot in-context learning (Y. Li, 2023), and we manually verified that
1159 no such effects occurred. Nonetheless, developing reliable validation strategies for
1160 spatiotemporal prompt optimisation remains an open research challenge.

1161 Simultaneously, both retrieval strategies – cell-based and score-based – could be
1162 further refined. We used the same disaster-relatedness classifier (Hanny et al., 2024) as
1163 for the hotspot detection approaches to ensure comparability between the approaches,
1164 while keeping inference times low due to the small model size. However, future work
1165 could explore the direct use of generative **LMs** for content assessment without such a
1166 prior filtering step. The score-based data retrieval method, specifically Eq. 6 might also
1167 be extended by a dynamic weighting mechanism, which integrates separate weights
1168 for spatial and temporal distance, as well as disaster-relatedness. In this context, the
1169 optimal weight configuration likely depends on the event. In an initial experiment, we
1170 varied the $w_{\text{spatial}} \in [0, 1]$ with $w_{\text{temporal}} = 1 - w_{\text{spatial}}$ and evaluated configurations
1171 with and without disaster-relatedness scores across our random validation subset. For
1172 the flood use case, macro F1 remained largely stable across all settings, with a slight
1173 advantage for configurations that included disaster-relatedness. For the wildfire case,
1174 higher temporal weighting led to marginal improvements. However, we also observed
1175 that these effects were inconsistent across different random subsets. To avoid overfit-
1176 ting to specific events, we therefore adopted equal weighting for spatial and temporal
1177 distance, reflecting the relevance of both dimensions in disaster contexts (Yabe, Tsub-
1178 ouchi, Fujiwara, Sekimoto, & Ukkusuri, 2020). The inclusion of disaster-relatedness
1179 in the score is furthermore supported by prior work demonstrating its importance for
1180 disaster detection tasks (Schmidt, Friedemann, et al., 2025).

1181 *Possible extensions*

1182 Another critical limitation of our methodology is that it currently does not account
1183 for the temporal dynamics of disasters. Instead, disaster predictions for each day are

1184 generated independently. Future work should explore modelling disaster detection as
1185 a temporal process, potentially using approaches like Markov chains (Trivedi, 2002).
1186 In preliminary experiments, we incorporated predictions from previous days into the
1187 context window of our LM approach, but this degraded performance due to high
1188 variability in day-to-day predictions. Beyond temporal modelling, it would also be
1189 valuable to integrate other data modalities such as visual content, and to investigate
1190 FMs beyond LMs, such as multimodal or time-series-oriented FMs.

1191 Finally, our study represents an initial implementation of LM-based disaster detec-
1192 tion, and several extensions are possible. Task-specialised multi-agent systems, as
1193 demonstrated by Han, Zhang, Yao, Jin, and Xu (2025), could improve reasoning
1194 performance by assigning separate sub-agents to process different data sources. Our
1195 statistical disaster detection methods could also be integrated as individual agents
1196 within such a framework. Moreover, multimodal LMs like Qwen3 (Yang et al., 2025)
1197 could incorporate visual information from images or videos to enhance situational
1198 awareness and geocoding accuracy (Schmidt, Díaz Fragachan, Arifi, Hanny, & Resch,
1199 2025). Beyond this, more advanced ensemble strategies such as meta-learning (Vet-
1200 toruzzo, Bouguelia, Vanschoren, Rögnvaldsson, & Santosh, 2024) should be explored,
1201 if possible, as our current implementation was limited to unsupervised voting methods.
1202 Lastly, fine-tuning generative LMs for disaster management, similar to domain-specific
1203 encoder models like CrisisBERT (Liu, Singhal, Blessing, Wood, & Lim, 2021), could
1204 substantially improve their ability to interpret digital traces and detect emerging
1205 disaster events.

1206 6 Conclusion

1207 In this paper, we investigated how Bluesky social media posts, GDELT news headlines
1208 and weather data can be used for identifying floods and wildfires as they occur. By
1209 framing the task of disaster detection as a binary classification problem on a resolu-
1210 tion 4 H3 grid, we quantified detection performance for several methods using class-1
1211 recall, macro F1 score, MCC and AUC-PR. Our analysis spanned the 2024 September
1212 floods in Central Europe and the 2025 Southern California wildfires. Satellite-derived
1213 flood and fire footprints served as reference data. We compared traditional statisti-
1214 cal hotspot and anomaly detection with a geospatial reasoning approach based
1215 on LMs, and evaluated how integrating multiple data modalities affected detection
1216 performance.

1217 Overall, our results show that both Bluesky posts and GDELT news headlines
1218 provide measurable, although limited, signals for detecting natural-hazard-induced
1219 disaster events. Using the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic, we achieved macro F1 scores of up to
1220 0.58 and MCC values up to 0.20, which aligns with Twitter-based findings by Schmidt,
1221 Friedemann, et al. (2025). GDELT performed slightly better than Bluesky, likely
1222 because news headlines more consistently reference affected locations. In contrast,
1223 weather anomaly detection produced near-random results (MCC ≈ 0.00). When the
1224 same data sources were analysed with our LM-based geospatial reasoning approach,
1225 performance improved substantially, reaching macro F1 scores up to 0.67 and MCC
1226 values up to 0.35. These findings effectively answer **RQ1**.

1227 Addressing **RQ2**, our multimodal **LM**-based geospatial reasoning approach sub-
1228 stantially outperformed all statistical baselines using only ten content items per
1229 prediction. Zero-shot configurations provided the best balance between precision and
1230 recall for both classes, with the score-based data retrieval variant performing best for
1231 the 2024 Central Europe floods and the cell-based retrieval variant for the 2025 South-
1232 ern California wildfires. This suggests that **LMS** can effectively interpret evidence from
1233 multiple heterogeneous sources and detect disaster events even when data are sparse.
1234 Few-shot learning increased class-1 recall from 0.34 to 0.63 for floods and from 0.30
1235 to 0.80 for wildfires, but at the cost of reduced precision and lower balanced evaluation
1236 metrics.

1237 For **RQ3**, we investigated the effect of combining multiple data sources. Mul-
1238 timodal integration generally improved disaster detection accuracy across both
1239 statistical and **LM**-based approaches, with the multimodal **LM** configurations out-
1240 performing all statistical ensembles. Combining Bluesky and **GDELT** data produced
1241 the most stable results across all disaster detection methods, suggesting that social
1242 and news media do indeed hold complementary information. However, single-source
1243 detection based on either of these two sources also performed strongly. Weather data
1244 added little predictive value on its own but modestly increased evaluation metrics
1245 when integrated into the geospatial reasoning approach. Simple ensemble voting of
1246 multiple approaches did not improve performance, underscoring the need for more
1247 advanced fusion methods such as meta-learning or multi-agent reasoning.

1248 To our knowledge, this is the first systematic, quantitative assessment of Bluesky
1249 and **GDELT** data for disaster detection and the first application of **FMS**, particularly
1250 generative **LMS**, for this purpose. Future work should focus on enhancing spatial
1251 granularity through improved geoparsing and develop more sophisticated training-free
1252 ensemble methods that can combine statistical and **FMS**-based methods. In a broader
1253 research context, our findings demonstrate that **FMS** hold substantial potential to
1254 serve as general-purpose event detectors for multimodal information streams.

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1275 **Data availability.** Our H3 evaluation grid, including satellite-derived indicators for
1276 disaster presence and statistics for each data source, will be made publicly available as
1277 a benchmark dataset on Zenodo upon acceptance of the manuscript. The raw Bluesky,
1278 [GDELT](#) and weather data can be acquired as described in Sec. 3.1.

1279 **Code availability.** All code for the methodology will be made publicly available
1280 on GitHub upon acceptance of the manuscript.

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1778 **Appendix A GDELT themes**

1779 Table [A1](#) depicts the themes used for news article crawling.

1780 **Appendix B Prompts**

1781 Figs. [B1](#) and [B2](#) visualise the user prompts for the two data retrieval strategies outlined
1782 in Sec. [3.4](#). Fig. [B3](#) depicts the human-designed system prompt and Fig. [B4](#) the
1783 optimised prompt after [APO](#).

Table A1 GDELT themes used for news article collection. The temporal boundaries for data collection are indicated in italics beneath the event headers.

2024 Central Europe floods <i>September 5-30, 2024</i>	2025 SoCal wildfires <i>December 24, 2024 - February 14, 2025</i>
WB_154_FLOOD_PROTECTION	NATURAL_DISASTER_WILDFIRE
NATURAL_DISASTER_FLOODWATERS	NATURAL_DISASTER_WILDFIRES
NATURAL_DISASTER_FLOODWATER	WB_1714_WILDFIRES_RISK_REDUCTION
NATURAL_DISASTER_FLOODS	NATURAL_DISASTER_FOREST_FIRE
NATURAL_DISASTER_FLOODING	NATURAL_DISASTER_FOREST_FIRES
NATURAL_DISASTER_FLOODED_ROADS	
NATURAL_DISASTER_FLOODED_ROAD	
NATURAL_DISASTER_FLOODED_AREAS	
NATURAL_DISASTER_FLOODED	
NATURAL_DISASTER_FLOOD_WATERS	
NATURAL_DISASTER_FLOOD_WATER	
NATURAL_DISASTER_FLOOD_WARNING	
NATURAL_DISASTER_FLOOD	
NATURAL_DISASTER_FLASH_FLOODS	
NATURAL_DISASTER_FLASH_FLOOD	

```

Cell-based retrieval

<event>
disaster event: {event_type}
Location: {centroid_location}
latitude: {latitude}
longitude: {longitude}
date: {current_date}
</event>

<social_media>
{total_posts} posts in the cell, {pct_disaster_related_posts}% disaster-related

Selected posts:
{top_posts}
</social_media>

<news>
{total_news} news articles in the cell, {pct_disaster_related_news}% disaster-related

Selected articles:
{top_news}
</news>

<weather>
temperature: {avg_temp_C} C
precipitation: {precipitation_mm}mm
wind speed: {wind_speed_kmh}km/h
</weather>

Analyse this data for event detection.

```

Fig. B1 User prompt for the cell-based data retrieval method.

Score-based retrieval

```
<event>
disaster event: {event_type}
Location: {centroid_location}
latitude: {latitude}
longitude: {longitude}
date: {current_date}
</event>

<social_media>
{total_posts} posts in the cell, {pct_disaster_related_posts}% disaster-related
Most relevant posts:
{top_posts}
</social_media>

<news>
{total_news} news articles in the cell, {pct_disaster_related_news}% disaster-related
Most relevant news articles:
{top_news}
</news>

<weather>
temperature: {avg_temp_C} C
precipitation: {precipitation_mm}mm
wind speed: {wind_speed_kmh}km/h
</weather>

Analyse this data for event detection.
```

Fig. B2 User prompt for the score-based data retrieval method.

1784 Appendix C Ground truth thresholds

1785 Fig C5 shows the fraction of disaster cells given different thresholds for detected flood
1786 blobs and wildfires based on satellite data.

Human-designed system prompt

```
You are an expert at detecting ongoing floods and wildfires.

You will receive data including:
- Social media posts (geoparsed)
- News articles (retrieved from GDELT)
- Weather observations

Your goal:
Identify if a flood or wildfire is actively occurring in the given H3 cell on the
specified date.
The grid cells are at resolution 4 with an edge length of 26.07 km.

Criteria:
- The event MUST be actively occurring NOW (no forecasts or predictions).
- Only confirm the event if supported by clear, direct, and credible evidence:
  - Explicit eyewitness reports
  - Official news confirmation
  - Recent weather data strongly indicative of the event (heavy rain causing flooding,
    recent heat and dryness for fires)
- Uncertain or ambiguous cases default to NO event.

Avoid:
- Inferring events solely from forecasts
- Overinterpreting ambiguous language
- Confirming based solely on indirect or speculative sources

The output should be a markdown code snippet formatted in the following schema, including
the leading and trailing "```json" and "```":

```json
{
 "event_detected": string // 0 or 1
 "event_probability": string // float 0-1
 "summary": string // <=60 characters
}
```

Fig. B3 System prompt designed by human experts.

## Machine-optimised system prompt

You are an expert in multi-source fusion for detecting active floods and wildfires.

**Objective**  
Decide if a flood or wildfire is actively occurring in the specified H3 cell (res 4, ~26 km edge) on the given date.  
Integrate social media, news (GDELT), and weather to maximize balanced precision/recall.

**Core principles**

- Require observed, current impacts. Forecasts or risk-only signals are insufficient.
- Fuse sources with explicit spatiotemporal thresholds, evidence strength tiers, and cross-source confirmation.
- Prefer cell-specific evidence; prevent regional bleed-over.
- Capture flood persistence/lag even after rain stops.

**Evidence preprocessing**

- Deduplicate: collapse reposts, quotes, duplicate articles, syndications; count unique sources/witnesses only.
- Filter out: historical/anecdotal ("in 2018," "used to"), meta/aftermath/aid-only content (fundraisers, celebrity visits) unless paired with current impacts; pure forecasts/watches/outlooks without observed effects.
- Extract: explicit place names, time references, event type (flood/wildfire), impact/operations terms (evacuations, closures, rescues, containment), and provided spatial/temporal distance.

**Spatiotemporal strength tiers**

- Time (relative to target date):
  - 0-12h: strong; 12-24h: strong; 24-72h: moderate for floods only; >72h: weak.
- Distance (to cell footprint):
  - Inside cell or <=15 km: strong; 16-40 km: moderate; 41-80 km: weak (supportive for floods only); >80 km: negligible.
- Geo-alignment: Favor evidence that names places inside the cell. For large regional wildfires, require explicit in-cell locality when source distance >20 km.

**Source reliability and content cues**

- Reliability (descending): official/local gov or emergency services; reputable local news; national news naming specific locality; verified eyewitness originals; unverified social/aggregators.
- Positive cues (boost): eyewitness photos/videos; "evacuations," "rescues," "road/bridge closed," "homes burning," "river overbank," "flash flood," "mudslide," "smoke column/flames visible," named active fire.
- Negative cues (penalize): "contained," "controlled," "evacuations lifted," "water receding," "drill," "prescribed burn," "planned burn."
- Language/time filters: downweight past tense tied to dated periods; upweight present progressive ("is flooding," "burning now").

**Weather integration**

- Flood signals:
  - Strong: 24h precip >=20-30 mm, or intense bursts (>=10 mm in 3h), or multi-day accumulations >=35-50 mm; recent river/urban drainage vulnerability indicators strengthen.
  - Persistence: allow active flooding up to 48-72h post-rain if any local/nearby impact reports exist.
- Wildfire signals:
  - Weather is supportive only (cannot confirm alone): hot/dry/windy (e.g., RH <25%, wind >8 m/s). Use to modestly raise probability when paired with observed fire impacts.
  - Do not confirm based solely on red flag warnings or dryness.

**Item-level scoring (normalize each evidence item)**

- Start from source reliability.
- Apply time and distance tier multipliers.
- Add/subtract for positive/negative cues.
- Classify item strength: strong, moderate, weak, or none.

**Cross-source confirmation rules (fusion)**

- Confirm event if any of:
  - >=1 strong news or official report naming an in-cell place within 24h.
  - >=2 independent strong eyewitness/social posts inside/<=15 km within 24h.
  - Flood: strong weather + >=1 credible local/nearby (<=50 km) flood impact <=48h.
  - Documented ongoing response (evacuations, rescues, closures due to flood/fire) inside/<=15 km <=48h.
- Do not confirm if:
  - Only forecasts/warnings or risk factors (dry/windy) without observed impacts.
  - Only regional coverage (>40 km) without in/near-cell alignment.
  - Only historical/meta content.

**Conflict and consistency handling**

- When sources disagree, prioritize direct, recent, in-cell observations and official updates.
- Apply negative cues to reduce probability unless contradicted by multiple strong in-cell observations.
- Avoid over-projecting a large regional event into adjacent cells without explicit in/near-cell evidence.

**Probability calibration and decision**

- 0.90-0.99: explicit in-cell official/eyewitness <=12h or multiple strong in-cell corroborations.
- 0.70-0.89: near-cell (<=15-20 km) corroboration across >=2 source types; or flood with strong rain + one local impact report (<=50 km).
- 0.60-0.69: single strong near-cell source; or flood persistence with moderate rain plus nearby reports.
- 0.40-0.59: weak or single-source remote evidence; insufficient for confirmation.
- <0.40: forecasts only, historical/meta, or regional with no local impacts.
- Set event\_detected = 1 if probability >=0.60; else 0.

**Geo-name and cell mapping**

- Match place names to the cell's footprint (neighborhoods, towns, landmarks).
- If evidence is 30-90 km away and no in/adjacent place is named, do not trigger.
- For coastal/river cells, consider upstream/downstream reports for floods within 48-72h if distances are <=50 km and impacts plausible.

Be conservative with remote/regional signals; be inclusive for floods with strong rainfall plus nearby impact reports within persistence windows.

The output should be a markdown code snippet formatted in the following schema, including the leading and trailing "```json" and "```":

```
```json
{
  "event_detected": string // 0 or 1
  "event_probability": string // float 0-1
  "summary": string // <=60 characters
}
```

Fig. B4 System prompt after APO.

Fig. C5 Relative fractions of disaster cells given different thresholds of detected flood blobs and wildfires.